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Social Lab Implementation Report 1: environmental and climate ethics issues in the context of R&I and for the green transition

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Executive Summary

This document provides the first report on the implementation activities of the RE4GREEN Social Labs, covering the period from May 2024 to April 2025. The RE4GREEN project, “Research Ethics and Integrity for the GREEN Transition,” focuses on supporting the European Commission to better integrate climate and environmental research ethics and research integrity considerations into its research and innovation programming. The Social Lab process was launched in April 2024 to bring together people from across sectors and R&I domains across the European Research Area, as well as from South Africa and Japan. These Social Labs create participatory spaces for exploring and addressing issues of environmental and climate ethics in the context of research and innovation (R&I) in general and for the Green Transition.

In this first phase, the Social Labs engaged in familiarization with Horizon Europe’s research and innovation funding structures, aligning their thematic areas with six Horizon Europe clusters, five missions, and several partnerships. This foundational work ensured that the Social Labs were well-integrated with the European Research Area (ERA) and focused on six thematic areas of Horizon Europe clusters. International perspectives from Japan and South Africa broadened the scope to global considerations of environmental and climate ethics.

Key activities during this phase included the recruitment of Social Lab participants by conducting more than 120 interviews with stakeholders across sectors, the design and facilitation of two participatory workshops across eight Social Labs. The findings from these activities revealed a range of significant issues. The interviews and first set of workshops highlighted cross-cutting concerns about resource use and intensity, the environmental impact of R&I practices, technoeconomic challenges, and justice and equity considerations amongst others. These first workshops revealed shared recognition of the tensions between driving technological and scientific innovation and minimizing environmental harm.

The second set of workshops delved deeper into the relationship between the issues identified and the goals of the European Green Transition. Participants engaged in reflective exercises discussing how their work in R&I advances and hinders the green transition. Participants also explored potential actions to address environmental and climate ethics issues from workshop 1. The second workshop highlighted the need for cross-sectoral collaboration, inclusive governance, and clearly defined responsibilities at all levels—from individual researchers to international policy frameworks. These workshop findings underscored the need for systemic reforms in governance, funding, and institutional priorities, as well as for fostering epistemic justice and broad participation to ensure diverse perspectives are integrated into decisions about the green transition.

This first phase of the Social Lab process has provided key inputs on guidelines and trainings to partner work packages and laid a foundation for the next stages of the RE4GREEN project. The first implementation phase surfaced key ethical challenges, fostered active R&I community engagement, and prepared for a deeper exploration of how to address climate and environmental issues in R&I. Upcoming workshops will gather feedback on policy recommendations and training materials developed by WP3 and WP4, as well as facilitate an exploration of the “do no significant harm” principle and how to better operationalize it in European research and innovation.

1 Scoping: Social Lab Implementation Report 1

Deliverable 2.2 is a first report on the implementation activities of the RE4GREEN Social Labs. The Social Lab process was launched in April 2024, with the delivery of the Deliverable 2.1 Social Lab Methodology (to be released in April 2026). The first implementation report focuses on desk research, interviews and social lab participants' views of environment and climate ethical issues in the context of European research and innovation (R&I) in general, and for the green transition in particular.

A Social Lab refers to a group of people gathered in common interest to address complex social challenges (Hassan, 2014), encompassing political, environmental, and technological. RE4GREEN gathers together people from across sectors and R&I domains in Europe, as well as South Africa and Japan, to grapple with issues of climate and environmental research ethics. The project's specific foci include not only R&I in general, but also in the context of green transition research.

Consequently, the setting of the RE4GREEN Social Labs is the European Research Area (ERA), and its main R&I funding programme, Horizon Europe. The RE4GREEN Social Labs gather researchers from across 6 Horizon Europe Clusters, 5 Missions, and many Partnerships. This first implementation report covers the period from 01.05.2024 – 30.04.2025, including:

- 1) Introducing the R&I context of each lab;
- 2) Presenting the method (briefly, the main part covered in the Methodology Deliverable 2.1) and results of social lab recruitment;
- 3) Synthesizing findings from interviews on climate and environmental ethics and integrity in R&I and for the European Green Transition specifically;
- 4) Synthesizing results from the first two participatory workshops held across the 8 RE4GREEN Social Labs;
- 5) Discussions of international comparison perspectives from the two social labs based in South Africa and Japan;
- 6) Presentation of next steps for the Social Labs, including a focus on:
 - a. Issues and responses related to the European Commission's "do no significant harm" principle;
 - b. Issues and responses related to assumptions and conduct of "Environmental Risk Assessments."

1.1 Introducing the Social Labs

The RE4GREEN Social Lab portfolio maps to European Commission R&I framework funding structures, in response to the initial funding call requirements to focus on the European Research Area (Figure 1).

* The European Institute of Innovation & Technology (EIT) is not part of the Specific Programme

Figure 1: Horizon Europe Framework Program Structure. The RE4GREEN Social Labs focus on Pillar II funding, as well as the Missions and Partnerships, not shown.

Beyond the European Research Area, the RE4GREEN Social Labs also include two International Companion Labs – one based in South Africa, at the University of Cape Town, and one based in Japan, at the University of Tokyo. The Social Labs also benefit from a general supporting partner based in the Republic of Korea at Korea University. The inclusion of International Companion Labs was selected to help reveal wider perspectives on climate and environmental ethics and research integrity issues – issues which themselves are often global in character.

Figure 2: Visualisation of RE4GREEN Social Labs and integration of the Social Lab work package (WP2) in the context of other project activities.

The RE4GREEN Social Labs cover Pillar II funding programmes of Horizon Europe (Figure 2).

Each Social Lab is led by a different RE4GREEN project partner (Table 1).

Institution	Lab no.	Lab focus
EARMA	1	Health, culture, and inclusive society; civil security (aligned with Social Lab 7)
AIT	2	Digital, industry and space
ECSA	3	Climate and mobility
AU	4	Energy
UAB	5	Fresh waters and oceans
UBO	6	Food, bioeconomy, agriculture, and environment; soil; natural resources (aligned with Social Lab 8)
U Tokyo	7	Health, culture, and inclusive society; civil security (aligned with Social Lab 1)
UCT	8	Food, bioeconomy, agriculture, and environment; soil; natural resources (aligned with Social Lab 6)

Table 1: Social Lab assignments within the RE4GREEN project.

The first phase of implementation involved Social Lab leaders based at each RE4GREEN partner organization familiarizing themselves with the scope of each Horizon Europe and broader ERA R&I funding area.

2 Familiarization Phase Results

2.1 Summary of themes covered by the Social Labs

Social Lab 1: Health, Culture, and Inclusive Society; Civil Security

The first social lab focuses on four interconnected themes: health, culture, inclusive society, and civil security. The health component encompasses a broad spectrum of research areas aimed at improving healthcare systems, addressing health disparities, and advancing medical breakthroughs. The culture and inclusive society theme seeks to foster social cohesion by addressing inequalities and promoting diversity. Research under this theme explores cultural heritage preservation, cultural exchange, and the empowerment of marginalized communities. It also delves into education, employment opportunities, and social integration strategies to create equitable societies that embrace inclusivity. The civil security for society component focuses on ensuring the safety and resilience of communities against various threats such as crime, terrorism, natural disasters, and cybersecurity breaches.

Social Lab 2: Digital, Industry and Space

This lab's theme builds upon Horizon Europe's Cluster 4: Digital, Industry, and Space. This cluster's overarching vision is to create competitive technologies that respect planetary limits while driving innovation in the digital sector, space technologies and industry. The research areas emphasize digital transformation, including artificial intelligence (AI), robotics, quantum computing, next-generation internet technologies, and advanced materials. These innovations aim to enhance industrial competitiveness while supporting sustainable practices. In the space sector, this cluster covers research on Earth observation technologies such as Copernicus services for climate monitoring and disaster management. It also explores innovative space applications for navigation, communication, and environmental research. The research topics in this lab include industry-specific challenges, such as transitioning to climate-neutral production systems through circular economy, and low-carbon technologies, sustainable materials production and resource efficiency.

Social Lab 3: Climate and Mobility

The theme of social lab 3 builds upon Horizon Europe's Cluster 5: Climate, Energy, and Mobility while focusing strictly on climate and mobility. The main aim behind Cluster 5's research and innovation activities on climate and mobility is to fight climate change by better understanding its causes, evolution, risks, impacts and opportunities, specifically by making the transport sectors more climate and environment-friendly, more efficient and competitive, smarter, safer and more resilient.

Social Lab 4: Energy

This lab covers research areas that aim to transform energy systems into sustainable models that align with climate neutrality goals. Research focuses on renewable energy technologies like

solar power while exploring efficient energy storage solutions such as batteries and carbon capture utilization/storage (CCUS) methods to mitigate emissions from industrial processes. Efforts in this research area are directed towards improving energy efficiency in buildings through smart technologies that reduce emissions. Citizen engagement, as a research method, plays a pivotal role in fostering public support for energy transitions.

Social Lab 5: Fresh Waters and Oceans

This lab covers research areas that work on critical challenges related to water conservation and ocean sustainability. Key themes include developing desalination plants for freshwater supply while mitigating environmental impacts such as brine discharge. Wastewater treatment innovations aim to reduce pollution while ensuring water quality standards are met. Ocean-related research explores sustainable fishing practices that minimize bycatch alongside aquaculture methods that reduce ecological footprints. Technologies like tidal energy plants are investigated for their potential in renewable energy generation while balancing ecosystem impacts. The lab also covers research areas that examines water-intensive activities like mining by promoting recycling technologies that reduce freshwater demand and pollution risks.

Social Lab 6: Food Systems; Bioeconomy; Agriculture; Environment; Soil; Natural resources

Social lab 6 explores research areas of Horizon Europe Cluster 6 (Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment). This cluster aims at reducing environmental degradation, halting and reversing the decline of biodiversity, and better managing natural resources through transformative changes of the economy and society in both urban and rural areas. It intends to ensure food and nutrition security for all within planetary boundaries through knowledge, innovation and digitalisation in agriculture and food systems, and steer and accelerate the transition to a low carbon, resource efficient circular economy and sustainable bioeconomy, including forestry.

Social Lab 7 (Japan): Health, Culture, and Inclusive Society; Civil Security

Sharing the Social Lab 1 themes of health, culture, inclusive society, and civil security, Social Lab 7 (U. Tokyo) covers environmental ethics, post-disaster reconstruction, community resilience, and rural revitalization. It focused on the social aspects of technological innovation, the ethical challenges of sustainability, and the intersection of human and non-human worlds. Some of the key thematic areas discussed were environmental justice and equity in decision-making, cultural construction of place and memory, and redefining nature in Japanese social and philosophical contexts.

Social Lab 8 (South Africa): Food Systems; Bioeconomy; Agriculture; Environment (as SL6)

Operating in South Africa, this lab covers research and development areas tailored to local contexts within Horizon Europe’s Clusters 5 (Climate) & 6 (Food Systems). Research areas include lab-grown meat production techniques for sustainable food systems alongside carbon credit initiatives for biodiversity conservation projects. Precision agriculture methods are explored to enhance smallholder farmer productivity using agroecology principles. Additionally, the lab is provisionally investigating decolonial ocean research under blue economy frameworks while addressing climate adaptation strategies through resilient agricultural practices.

2.2 Funding connected to Social Labs

To date, 4053 projects have been funded by the European Commission under Horizon Europe’s Pillar II clusters, accounting for 25,95 B EUR contribution in total (Figure 3). The Horizon Europe budget distribution directly shaped the structure of the Social Labs, with higher-funded clusters like Climate, Energy and Mobility being split across several labs (Social Labs 3 and 4). Digital, Industry and Space informed Social Lab 2, while Food, Bioeconomy, and Environment guided the themes of Social Labs 6 and 8. Smaller clusters—Health, Culture and Inclusive Society, and Civil Security—were combined in Social Labs 1 and 7. Topics of high environmental importance, such as oceans and freshwater, received dedicated attention in Social Lab 5.

Overview by programme/pillar/thematic priority/keyword

Figure 3 Funding amounts allocated per Horizon Europe clusters until 01.05.2024., source: <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/horizon-dashboard>

2.3 Direct connections to the Green Transition

The RE4GREEN Social Labs address a wide range of research and innovation (R&I) areas, many of which are directly linked to the Green Transition. This section of the report makes those connections explicit by examining how each Social Lab's theme aligns with the goals of the Green Transition, as outlined in the European Green Deal. Below is a summary of the Green

Transition goals, followed by an overview of how each Social Lab theme connects to these objectives.

2.3.1 Green Transition goals

a) Clean, Affordable, and Secure Energy

With [Clean, Affordable, and Secure Energy](#), the EU aims to decarbonise the energy system by aiming to achieve “net-zero greenhouse gas emissions by 2050.”

The key principles include:

- to prioritise energy efficiency
- to develop a power sector based largely on renewable resources (e.g., offshore wind and hydrogen)
- to secure an affordable EU energy supply
- and to have a fully integrated, interconnected digitalised EU energy market

b) Sustainable Industry and Circular Economy

By introducing the [European Industrial Strategy](#) and [Circular Economy Action Plan](#) the EU aims to "empower citizens, revitalise regions and have the best technologies" and to explore and create “climate neutral” circular economy-friendly goods markets.

The key principles include:

- to boost the decarbonisation and modernisation of industries (especially, carbon-intensive industries such as steel and cement)
- to reduce wastage of materials: reusable and recyclable materials including textiles, construction, vehicles, batteries, electronics and plastics
- to aim stopping exporting waste outside of the EU

c) Sustainable Living (Building and Renovation)

With the [Renovation Wave Strategy](#), the EU is targeting the process of building and renovation in regard to their currently unsustainable methods, and is promoting sustainable living.

The key principles include:

- to promote the use of energy-efficient building methods such as climate-proofing buildings
- to increase digitalisation and enforce rules surrounding the energy performance of buildings
- to triple the renovation rate of all buildings to reduce pollution
- To promote social housing renovation, smart city mobility, environmental monitoring, and catastrophe prediction (e.g., [New European Bauhaus](#))

d) Safer and More Sustainable Chemicals

Chemicals may be essential for modern living, but their production and use can pose risks to human health and the environment. The [EU Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability](#), adopted in March 2021, outlines a long-term vision for a safer and more sustainable chemical industry.

Key goals include:

- Enhanced protection of human health.
- Strengthening industry competitiveness.
- Supporting a toxic-free environment.

e) Sustainable Food Production

The [Farm to Fork Strategy](#) pursues the issue of food sustainability and the support to the producers, i.e. farmers and fishermen. The methods of production and transfer of these resources are what the E.U. considers a climate-friendly approach, aiming to increase efficiency as well.

Targets by 2030 are:

- Making 25% of EU agriculture organic.
- Reduce by 50% the use of pesticides.
- Reduce the use of fertilizers by 20%.
- Reduce nutrient depletion by at least 50%.
- Reduce the use of antimicrobials in agriculture and antimicrobials in aquaculture by 50%.
- Create sustainable food labelling.
- Reduce food waste by 50%.

f) Eliminating pollution

The '[Zero Pollution Action Plan](#)' aims to achieve no pollution from "all sources", cleaning the air, water and soil by 2050.

The targets include:

- improving air quality to reduce the number of premature deaths caused by air pollution by 55%.
- improving water quality by reducing waste, plastic litter at sea (by 50%) and microplastics released into the environment (by 30%).
- improving soil quality by reducing nutrient losses and chemical pesticide use by 50%.
- reducing by 25% the EU ecosystems where air pollution threatens biodiversity.
- reducing the share of people chronically disturbed by transport noise by 30%.
- significantly reducing waste generation and by 50% residual municipal waste.

g) Sustainable Mobility

A comprehensive strategy "[Sustainable and Smart Mobility](#)" includes targets to make mobility "sustainable", "smart", and "resilient" by 2030-2050:

- to increase the adoption of sustainable and alternative fuels in road, maritime, and air transport.
- to fix the emission standards for combustion engine vehicles.
- to develop smart traffic management systems and applications.
- to alter freight delivery methods with the preferred pathways being by land or water.
- to increase public transport alternations to reduce public congestion and pollution.
- to increase electric charging ports to encourage the purchase of low-emission vehicles.
- to develop a single European air traffic management system to increase safety, flight efficiency, and environmentally friendly conditions.

h) Climate Adaptation

Recognizing the inevitability of some climate change impacts, the [EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change](#) focuses on building a climate-resilient Europe by 2050.

Key areas of action include:

- Enhanced data collection and sharing: improved access to and exchange of knowledge on climate impacts for effective adaptation strategies.
- Nature-based solutions: the use of nature-based solutions to help climate resilience and protect ecosystems.
- Integration of adaptation into macro-fiscal policies: incorporating adaptation considerations into broader economic and fiscal planning.

i) Restore Biodiversity

[EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030](#) tackles the critical issue of biodiversity loss in Europe, aiming to achieve a reversal by 2030.

Key actions within this strategy include:

- Expanding protected land and sea areas.
- Restoring degraded ecosystems by reducing pesticide use, including forest restorations.
- Increased funding and monitoring.

j) Just Transition

[A Just Transition Mechanism](#): The transition to a low-carbon economy will vary in difficulty across EU member states and regions. Some regions are heavily reliant on fossil fuels or carbon-intensive industries, potentially facing significant social and economic challenges during the transition. The EU provides financial and technical support (€55 billion mobilisation over the period 2021-2027) to address the concern focusing on:

- People and communities: facilitating job creation and reskilling initiatives, improving energy efficiency in housing, and combating energy poverty.
- Companies: making a shift to low-carbon technologies more financially attractive. Financial support and fosters investment in R&I.
- Member states or regions: investing in new green jobs, sustainable public transport, digital connectivity, and clean energy infrastructure

Social Lab connections to the Green Transition

The Social Labs in diverse thematic areas are making various contributions to the European Green Deal, each advancing an important theme on sustainability, resilience, and innovation. Below is an overview of each Social Lab in relation to the GT.

Social Lab 1 - Health, Culture and Civil Security (EARMA)

SL1 focuses on strengthening health system sustainability, cultural engagement, and civil resilience. These areas of focus invest in a green transition that addresses environmental health impacts, eco-friendly practices under cultural heritage sustainability, and preparedness for climatic risks.

Social Lab 2 - Digital, Industry and Space (AIT)

The theme of SL2 contributes to the green transition by introducing resourceful and circular industrial practices with low-emission technologies and greener data infrastructures. Innovations in manufacturing, advanced materials, and digital systems contribute to decarbonizing the industry and improving resource efficiency and environmental monitoring by space-based systems like Copernicus.

Social Lab 3 - Climate and Mobility (ECSA)

In advancing climate science and zero-emission mobility, this lab's theme promotes well-integrated responses to climate change, including sustainable transport and climate-resilient infrastructure. R&I in the covered research area advances adaptation and mitigation approaches, clean mobility, and active citizen participation in climate actions.

Social Lab 4 - Energy (AU)

By promoting clean and inclusive energy systems, this lab covers topics on renewable energy and energy efficiency in buildings and industry, as well as breakthroughs in energy technology such as batteries and hydrogen. Research in this area is considered to play a very important function in the road to climate neutrality focusing on developing decentralized, sustainable energy models.

Social Lab 5 - Fresh Waters and Oceans (UAB)

SL5's theme in alignment with the green transition focuses on exploring innovative approaches to water conservation and marine protection. Initiatives within this theme promote responsible water management strategies to ensure efficient use and protection of freshwater resources.

Furthermore, efforts are directed towards protecting marine ecosystems from overexploitation and pollution. Promoting sustainable fisheries and safeguarding ocean health is of key importance under this theme.

Social Lab 6 - Food, Agriculture and Bioeconomy (UBO)

The research agenda in SL6 covers bio-based systems, sustainable food production, and circular economy practices towards the ecological transition. It is supportive of biodiversity and mitigation of GHG emissions from agriculture and forestry while making food systems healthier and more sustainable. It greatly aligns with EU policies such as the Farm to Fork strategy and the Biodiversity Strategy for 2030.

International Social Labs

The connection of the Social Labs operating in South Africa and Japan will be addressed and elaborated on in the 2nd implementation report. In brief detail, the South Africa lab is exploring the connection between EU and African Union research and innovation as it relates to food and agriculture research for the green transition (in South Africa). These changes were realized as necessary to enhance the relevance of the social lab's remit in light of the South African research context. The Japan lab is exploring civil security, resilience and health in relation to disaster recovery and connected research and innovation. This change was considered necessary to further connect climate and environmental ethics issues and the green transition to the Japanese context, where EU R&I policy and the EU Green Deal have more tangential relevance to national and regional policies.

3 Interview Results

3.1 Interview reach and scope

This section presents the findings from 124 interviews conducted across eight social labs between June and December 2024. The interview data below focuses on results connected to climate and environmental ethics and research integrity issues and the green transition. Data related to interviewee's perspective on the utility of guidelines and trainings will be reported on in separate RE4GREEN deliverables related to these topics directly.

The interviews aimed to explore how researchers, project leaders, and representatives from diverse sectors understand and engage with climate and environmental ethics and research integrity within their field. It sought to uncover awareness of related issues, existing guidelines or efforts to address them, and how these topics intersect with broader initiatives like the European Green Deal and the Green Transition. Questions focused on personal experiences, current practices, available training, and what kinds of knowledge, skills, or support would be most helpful moving forward.

All interviews were conducted with informed consent of participants in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation, EU Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR), using a consent form (Annex 1 – Interview Consent Form) reviewed and approved by the German Reference Centre for Ethics in the Life Sciences. The Research Ethics Committee at UAB requested minor modifications to the Consent Form in accordance with current participatory research standards, resulting in the necessary ethics approval. AU applied for ethics approval for SL4 at Aarhus University for the study RE4GREEN, Social Lab on Energy, and it was approved by the Institutional Review Board at Aarhus University, approval no. BSS-2024-098-L.

The gender distribution of participants included 74 females, 49 males, and 1 non-binary individual. A breakdown of participation by sector is presented in Figure 4, below; geographic breakdown in Figure 5.

Figure 4: Interview participation by sector

Figure 5: Geographic distribution of interview participation. Geographical distribution of interviewees: Austria: 4, Belgium: 6, Chile: 3, Cyprus: 1, Czech Republic: 2, Denmark: 3, Estonia: 1, Finland: 2, France: 1, Germany: 21, Greece: 4, Hungary: 2, Iceland: 1, Ireland: 2, Italy: 5, Japan: 7, Kazakhstan: 1, Kenya: 1, Latvia: 2, Luxembourg: 4, Netherlands: 5, Norway: 8, Poland: 1, Portugal: 3, South Africa: 7, Spain: 10, Sweden: 3, Switzerland: 2, Uganda: 1, UK: 6, USA: 3, South Korea: 1. Note, Social Lab 6, based in Germany, faced recruitment difficulties in the broader EU, thus over-representing recruitment of interviews in Germany.

3.1.1 Interview method and analysis

Each of the project partners were tasked with conducting interviews with relevant stakeholders on behalf of the project team. In each case, partners used a mix of existing networks and desktop research to identify and contact suitable interviewees. The aim was to gather a broad slate of relevant voices from across sectors and thematic areas and geographies.

The interviews followed a structured format to ensure consistency and comparability across results. At the same time some flexibility was given to interviewers to follow up on relevant points or insights raised by the participants. This balance helped the project team to gather rich and comparable data, whilst also accounting for context specific differences across Social Lab themes.

The interview findings were summarised by the partners leading each social lab, who compiled individual interview reports based on the conversations they held. Each partner then analysed these reports to identify main climate and environmental ethics issues and concerns raised by participants. After this initial step, the research team at AIT brought the results from all labs together and carried out a cross-lab analysis, clustering similar issues to identify common themes. To make sure nothing was overlooked, AIT shared the clustered results with the partners for feedback. For this report, we did not analyse the responses regarding existing guidelines, efforts, and trainings that address climate and environmental ethics issues in R&I, instead, we forwarded the relevant material to Work Packages 3 and 4.

3.2 Interview results

In this section, we present how interviewees conceptualized research ethics and integrity in general and list the **environment and climate ethical issues in the context of European research and innovation** that were raised by interviewees across the different social labs. The findings reflect a range of concerns and challenges identified by participants during the interviews, as summarised, analysed, and synthesised through the collaborative process described above.

A total of 10 issue areas were collected across the social labs: resource use and intensity; technoeconomic challenges (related to scaling social and technological solutions); competing needs and priorities (related to the exigencies of transition and the impact of technologies used to achieve it); environmental impact; justice and equity; impacts of technologies on animals; resource use in research practice; gender dimension; epistemic justice; and bureaucracy (in the case of one lab in particular). For each issue, a short description follows, below, along with exemplary illustrative quotations from various social lab participant interviews.

The definition of research ethics and integrity

Interviewees offered varied conceptualizations of research ethics and research integrity; some did not offer any formal or simple definition. Research ethics was typically described as an ethical system for responsible research conduct, specifically in relation to human and animal subjects, the environment, and broader societal implications. Research integrity was most commonly described as part of ethics, with focus on openness, honesty, and accountability in research.

Without strict definitions, interviewees often referred to related practices such as data protection, informed consent, fair authorship, and responsible communication of research findings.

Issue 1: Resource use/intensity

The energy demands of technologies and infrastructures are significant, highlighting resource and energy consumption not just during use, but throughout their entire life cycles—from development and deployment to maintenance and eventual disposal.

"What we see is that products are not made to be repaired at all... so we need to extract cobalt, gold, copper, and all of this in more and more places." – SL2, Portugal, Circular Economy, CSO

"These new forms of art [digital art] are extremely expensive in terms of energy. In addition, people are used to sell and buy goods in person, having physical objects in front of them" – SL1, Italy, Law, HEI

"We can massively reduce global emissions if Europe, the United States, and China agreed to only use combined cycle, natural gas power plants... but countries may not want to make agreements where these technologies are delivered in an open-access way." – SL3, Norway, Combustion, Fluid Mechanics, Decarbonization, HEI

"That's our focus—trying to reuse materials that exist, like building waste materials, and there's a lot of problems. There's no protocols, there's no standards to guarantee the security. So there's a need for a framework that is serious and consistent at the research level, in order to inform policy, if I'm going to reuse concrete in a structural way" – SL4, Denmark, Building energy efficiency and indoor environmental quality, HEI

"The biggest problem, in my opinion, is that the cities use more resources as are available to them which leads to exploitation of the rural areas. That applies especially to their usage of water, and they produce more waste than they can deal with." – SL6, Hungary, precision farming / nature-based solutions, CSO

Issue 2: Technoeconomic challenges

This issue refers to systemic economic pressures that hinder the adoption of environmentally responsible technologies. These include cost barriers, lack of incentives, entrenched market dynamics, and limited funding for green alternatives. Even when greener options exist, competing economic priorities often prevent their integration.

"With green public procurement you want to make sure you also have buyers for green steel products because at the moment [...] it's a bit difficult" – SL2, Belgium, Decarbonization of industry, CSO

"We aim to produce evidence-based solutions that contribute to sustainable and equitable mobility, rather than solutions biased towards specific groups with financial interests." – SL3, United Kingdom, Transport policies, sustainable mobility, public engagement, HEI

"Ethics or sustainability are not prioritized over economic development." – SL5, Chile, Water management - AI, RTO

"I think that if we are seriously going to make a green transition, we need to figure out how to have more circular economies and degrowth in ways that are not extremely harmful to people's economic wellbeing and I'm not convinced we figure that out yet." – SL5, USA, Research in water insecurity, HEI

Issue 3: Competing needs and priorities

This issue is describing the tension between driving innovation and minimizing environmental harm. It includes justifying harm for scientific progress, balancing technological advancement with planetary limits, and navigating conflicts between local needs and global goals—especially in sectors like energy and infrastructure.

"It's about transforming our existing buildings to meet new needs, even as populations grow, and transforming the way we use space. Data even shows that in Danish society, for example, 20 years ago people lived in smaller apartments than they do now. So, using existing structures to increase density makes sense, but it's also at odds with people's expectations." – SL4, Denmark, Building energy efficiency and indoor environmental quality, HEI

"I asked a guy at a conference, you know, how are you going to recycle the wind turbines when they come to the end of their life? And his response was, 'Oh well, by the time we get to that stage, we'll have figured that out.' So there's that attitude of, yes, we need to move quickly to decarbonize, but there's also the danger of rushing into things and making it very difficult to pick apart the issues they leave behind." – SL4, UK, Water treatment in battery recycling and lithium mining, RTO

"lots of the coal mines have established a community who are dependent on this economy, schools, public health and informal and formal activities, so what happened when the mine is shut down and we move into other issues [...] I don't think we have ticked all the boxes to ensure that the people that are affected the most by these transitions have been allocated the time of day to be able to move in that way" – SL 8, South Africa, Science & Innovation, Nat-GOV

Issue 4: Environmental impact

Environmental impact covers the direct ecological consequences of research and technology development, including pollution, waste, toxicity, habitat destruction, and resource depletion. It also reflects concerns about mining, deep-sea extraction, obsolescence, and contributions to climate change.

"There's some inherent damage in the experiment itself [of testing deep-sea mining] ... even on the video, the impact was visible with clouds of sediment and the sea floor being squashed." – SL2, Science Journalism, Ireland, Media

"Pharma manufacturing must be very cognizant of matters such as waste disposal (wastewater, leftover human tissues/specimens, chemicals) and follow ethical and legal practices. Also, we are aware of the environmental impact of our packaging" - SL1, USA, Health and Env. Protection, LMNE

"Project officers...think in terms of science, you know...They are much more concerned with methodologies or technical aspects...but not that much on following...which research results or solutions are contributing the most to the impacts." – SL3, Germany, Exploitation in projects of Smart City eMobility and Hydroelectricity, RTO

"They mentioned that the tides are rising, which is causing greater erosion. Archaeological sites are falling into the sea, and they have no way to safeguard them." – SL5, Chile – Rapa Nui, Indigenous Peoples, HEI

Issue 5: Justice and equity

This issue focuses on disparities in who benefits from technological progress versus who bears the costs. This includes geographic, social, and economic inequalities—such as "carbon colonialism", child labour in mining, or rural communities hosting wind farms without reaping benefits. It calls for fair transitions that consider power, privilege, and historic injustices.

"So, we need to bring everybody in this transition, which is very difficult because people are in very different levels of development ... or in different levels of quality of life."– SL2, Portugal, Circular economy, CSO

"HIV positive, who have lack of housing, almost like 70% who the participants from marginalized populations, who we enroll in our report, they lack their own housing. I think they are disproportionately affected by this climate change. Especially if it's a housing instability during extreme events and conditions like we have in Kazakhstan. Additionally, they have lack access to healthcare infrastructure." - SL1, Kazakhstan, Social Work, RTO

"There is an emphasis on the importance of minimizing the environmental impact and in promoting equity and inclusion in transport innovations." – SL3, United Kingdom, Transport policies, sustainable mobility, public engagement, HEI

"A smallholder farmer who farms on two or three hectares in sub-Saharan Africa with very little machinery or even any machineries, mostly household labor – They should not be thinking about mitigation. It's really not ethically right for them to be thinking about mitigation." – SL6, United Kingdom, small-holder agriculture and livelihood, REC

"Social justice is something that will definitely affect and be affected by the scale-up of carbon removal in Europe." – SL3, Germany, Carbon dioxide reduction, RTO

"We work a lot with the leaving no one behind principle, I'm not sure if this goes into the research integrity, but this is something we try to keep in mind in every step of the research, to ensure inclusivity." – SL5, Norway, Coastal Communities, HEI

Issue 6: Impacts of technologies on animals

Raises ethical questions about how emerging technologies affect nonhuman life, especially animals used in research, food production, or labour. It encompasses the issues of animal rights and welfare, especially in contexts like lab-grown meat, automation in farming, and biotechnology development.

"...actually, the reason why I started this company was to reimagine a world where we can develop delicious meat products without the need of killing animals. So, ethics for us is essentially the one thing of removing animals from the supply chain of our food without compromising nutrition, flavour, and the consumer's experience."- SL8, South Africa, Lab-made meat, Private company

"EU has banned the selling of... you're not allowed to sell seals, to protect the species, but it's grown the species population, and the Baltic has grown so much after the ban that it's creating a lot of trouble for small scale fisheries and kind of traditional fishing practises in [Locatin]." – SL5, Norway, Coastal Communities, HEI

Issue 7: Resource use in research practice

Research activities themselves consume energy and materials—such as data storage, lab operations, and academic travel. There's a growing call to green research practices, reduce unnecessary mobility, and account for emissions and environmental footprints within the research process itself.

"Experts and researchers have not completely adapted to the new digital scenario, but they continue to prefer travelling for meetings and to know each other with the goal of building trust and confidence among them" – SL1, Italy, Law, HEI

"We try to use our supercomputer at its maximum level... we always try to be at 98% of usage." – SL2, Germany, Space and earth observation, Public Sector

"We were trying to compensate, for example, for the CO₂ produced by travel of the jury members. But this is very unfortunate, and we are very unhappy about it because the legal department told us we cannot use our budget for CO₂ compensation." – SL1, Austria, Physics RFO

"Apart from the actual, let's say, meetings and the travels associated with the projects themselves because "Project X", for example, wants people to meet at each meeting in person and it's twice per year." – SL3, Germany, Environmental law & justice, citizen science, CSO

"And so something I did that wasn't very popular at the conference that I hosted this year was I made the food entirely vegan, as a kind of stance towards climate change and so on." – SL8, South Africa, Environmental ethics, HEI

Issue 8: Gender dimension

This issue recognizes that environmental risks, access to resources, and participation in decision-making are not evenly distributed across genders. Women and gender minorities often face greater environmental harm and are underrepresented in shaping technological responses.

"Local action groups, like energy communities, are very male dominated and very technical. [...] Given the marginalization of women in STEM and energy-related fields, many local action groups say women find it very hard to submit a proposal to get funding because they don't have the technical expertise [...] Whereas you know men, they will hire project consultants to write it for them and get the grant." – SL4, UK, Environmental social scientist focusing on justice aspects of energy transitions, HEI

"We have also started working on a study that includes the gender dimension, because impacts and risks are often asymmetric across different genders. So, I believe that including this social and gender aspect would be essential." – SL5, Spain, Environmental sciences, GO

Issue 9: Epistemic Justice

Epistemic justice is about recognizing whose knowledge is valued and ensuring that all voices - especially those from marginalized groups - are heard and respected. It challenges the dominance of expert or Western perspectives by valuing lived experience and indigenous ways of knowing.

"The corporates and the government are, of course, the most powerful. The way they treat knowledge is basically grafted onto the way academic science makes knowledge [...] So that means that the perspective and the knowledge system of the farmers lacks any recognition and fails to get the acknowledgement that it deserves." – SL4, The Netherlands, Science and technologies studies with a focus on epistemic justice, HEI

"Because we're right down on the ground, we see that there's a lot of power dynamics that relates to funding around research, around decision making, and the voices of people on the ground are not well heard, they're not well understood, and there isn't the time to actually take them forward." – SL8, South Africa, Carbon credits, NGO/CSO

Issue 10: Bureaucracy

National and supra-national regulations can be a valuable tool to implement the objectives of the green transition. However, they are likely to become obstacles for the green transition or unnecessary burdens for innovators if designed uninformed of the practices to which they apply. This issue was discussed in detail in SL6.

"The objectives of the European Green Deal are well intended, but far from the practice. Bureaucracy undermines most of its objectives and it has to be readjusted in a way that makes it practicable. Without practicability it is impossible to achieve broad acceptance." - SL6, Germany, Agriculture, GO

"As I see it, private companies are frustrated over the bureaucracy, especially with the ESG reporting: The environmental impact assessment has to be done by companies, which is very problematic because it is being demanded from persons who do not have environmental knowledge, which is very unproductive. The frustration of private companies has negative effects on the Green Transition and in some cases leads to green washing. I am very unhappy about this." - SL6, Estonia, Sustainability/Urban Biodiversity Management, HEI

4 Social Lab Workshop 1

Social Lab Workshop 1 aimed at exploring different perspectives on environmental and climate ethics and integrity issues and gathering insights on how these issues come into play in R&I practice in general. The WS1 was aimed at sharing and validating the interview findings. As reported in the Social Lab Manual, workshop 1 content was aimed at supplementing the activities of Task 1.1: Identify key concepts and issues in environmental and climate ethics for R&I, led by UT (02.01.2024–31.05.2025). Also, the content was developed to supplement the activities of Task 4.1: Develop training materials, led by VUMC (30.06.2024–31.03.2025).

Additionally, workshop 1 focused on familiarising the Social Lab methodologies (e.g., scope of SL, online tools) and building a community for each SL so that the participants could feel comfortable to engage with the succeeding workshops. All the workshops were conducted online, except for the University of Tokyo Lab. For the half-day online workshops, we used the online digital whiteboard “[Mural](#)” for collaborative and interactive work. The University of Tokyo Lab used adopted and printed versions of the same workshop format for an in-person workshop. The workshops were conducted from December 2024 to mid-February 2025 across the SLs.

4.1 Aims and scope

To explore environmental and climate ethics and research integrity issues in R&I practice, and to get familiar with the Social Lab methodology, Workshop 1 was designed by the AIT team as follows. The first 40 min. were dedicated to an icebreaker and introductory session. This allowed participants to get to know the workshop agenda and the online tool being used for facilitation and data collection. Then, we introduced the key issues from the interviews as a preliminary result input to the conversation. Participants were asked to review and validate the identified issues, with particular attention to any that may have been overlooked—especially those specific to R&I/technology area in each SL. The refined set of issues was then evaluated based on their relevance to the participants’ R&I or technological focus areas. Following this, we visualised the significance of each Issue and invited participants to share personal narratives related to the Issues they found most meaningful. These activities were designed to establish a strong connection between the participants’ R&I practices and the issues under discussion.

In the next session, the focus shifted to exploring the underlying causes and contributing factors of the Issues. To facilitate this, we conducted role-playing breakout sessions, encouraging participants to engage from different perspectives. The workshop concluded with a plenary discussion, outlining next steps and collecting participant feedback.

Throughout the workshop, we used a colour-and-number coding system to label participants’ sticky notes for data traceability—excluding sensitive or identifying data.

4.2 Participation in Workshop 1

Following the interviews, the Social Lab participants were invited to join the workshops. To expand the coverage of the participation, we recruited additional participants. All workshops were conducted with informed consent of participants in accordance with the General Data

Protection Regulation, EU Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR), using a consent form (Annex 2 – Workshop Consent Form) reviewed and approved by the German Reference Centre for Ethics in the Life Sciences. The Research Ethics Committee at UAB requested minor modifications to the Consent Form in accordance with current participatory research standards, resulting in the necessary ethics approval. The same was the case for AU who applied for ethics approval for SL4 at Aarhus University for the study RE4GREEN, Social Lab on Energy, and it was approved by the Institutional Review Board at Aarhus University, approval no. BSS-2024-098-L.

In total, we had 61 participants across the SLs. The gender distribution of participants included 37 females, 23 males, and 1 non-binary individual.

Participation by sectors were research performing (62%), civil society and media (15%), public sector including funders and research ethics committees (10%), private sector (8%), and other (5%) (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Workshop 1 participation by sector.

Most participants were from Europe, with some joining from other regions as well. The geographic locations of the participants' organisations covered most of Central, Western, Northern, and Southern Europe. Additionally, we invited participants from Japan (SL7), South Africa (SL8), and other countries including USA, India, Kenya, Uganda, Morocco, and Chile (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Geographical distribution of WS1 participants. Austria:4, France: 1, Latvia: 2, Portugal: 2, Spain: 7, Switzerland: 2, Belgium: 2, Czech Republic: 1, Germany: 6, Luxemburg: 1, Greece: 1, Cyprus: 1, Italy: 1, Netherlands: 2, Finland: 2, Croatia: 1, Norway: 2, Sweden: 1, India: 1, UK: 1, Denmark: 1, Ireland: 1, Estonia: 1, Chile: 2, USA: 2, South Africa: 7, South Korea: 1, Japan: 4, South Africa: 2, Uganda: 1, Kenya: 1, Morocco: 1 (If the participants have double affiliations or their organisations have multiple locations, we counted all of them.)

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4.3 Results

The results of WS1 validated the interview results and deepened our understanding of climate and environmental ethics and integrity issues in R&I practices. The results also show how participants evaluated the significance of the issues presented. Despite each SL having different thematic areas and focuses, the participants showed similar interests and concerns across the SLs. WS 1 also revealed a variety of reasons and causes of climate and environmental issues. Based on their experience, many participants addressed structural and systematic issues that made the change challenging.

4.3.1 Participant perspectives on the significance of climate and environmental ethics and integrity issues across social labs

Figure 8: Screenshot of the exercise on the significance of climate and environmental issues. Note the addition of Epistemic Justice and Bureaucracy emerged more prominently after the workshop.

After the introduction and ice breaker exercise, the participants were asked to indicate the significance of the issues in their field or work by placing four different indicators: “Very relevant”, “Relevant”, “Only a little relevant”, and “Not relevant”. The result across the Social Labs on the cross-cutting issues is summarised in the table 2. In the table, the values of the issues were colour-scaled from the highest value to the lowest value in each lab.

The results illustrate the commonalities and differences across the Social Labs. Overall, "Environmental impact" and "Justice and equity" were highlighted as of high significance across all the Social Labs. "Impacts of technologies on animals" showed the least significance. "Resource use/Intensity", "Technoeconomic challenges", and "competing needs and priorities" are also addressed as relatively high-significance issues, except for SL1. "Gender dimension" was not addressed as particularly significant in SL2 and SL6 whereas it shows relatively higher indications in the other Labs. "Resource use in research practice" was considered more significant in SL5 than in other Labs. Besides the presented cross-lab issues, we asked the participants whether they perceived any issues to be missing from the list (Table 2).

	Resource use/intensity	Technoeconomic challenges	Competing needs and priorities	Environmental impact	Justice and equity	Impacts of technologies on animals	Resource use in research practice	Gender dimension
SL1: Health, culture, and inclusive society; civil security	12%	5%	12%	20%	20%	9%	10%	12%
SL2: Digital, Industry and Space	15%	15%	10%	18%	15%	11%	12%	5%
SL3: Climate and Mobility	14%	14%	13%	14%	20%	8%	7%	11%
SL 4: Energy	15%	15%	15%	15%	16%	4%	9%	11%
SL5: Fresh waters and ocean	11%	14%	13%	16%	13%	7%	14%	13%
SL6: Food, bioeconomy, agriculture and environment; soil; natural resources	12%	12%	14%	20%	17%	10%	7%	9%
SL7: Health, culture, and inclusive society; civil security	15%	15%	13%	15%	13%	6%	15%	6%
SL8: Food, bioeconomy, agriculture, and environment; soil; natural resources	12%	12%	14%	15%	16%	8%	10%	13%
All Labs	13%	13%	13%	16%	16%	8%	10%	10%

Table 2: Participants' emphasis on issues (percentages indicate total expression of significance for a given issue, divided by all expressions of significance within the particular social lab). Scores are based on participants' expression of "Very relevant", "Relevant", "Only a little relevant", and "Not relevant", "weighted, respectively, 3, 2, 1, and 0, and then multiplied by the numbers of the expressions. SL7 counted the total of the participants' agreements on the significances, which were quantified in a comparative way. Each value was divided by the total value in each lab.

Additional issues discussed:

Social Lab 1:

Issue	Description
Diversity	In addition to the gender dimension, diversity was proposed as a common issue. Inequalities exist beyond gender, namely LGBTIAQ+, older and younger people.
Socio-environmental impact	Different social groups have different influences, decision-making power, interests, or vulnerability. Those differences among the social groups are also related to the environmental impact assessment.

Social Lab 2:

Issue	Description
Transparency and access to environmental data	Governments sometimes hide environmental data, and citizens' data literacy depends on education and social status.
Condition and health monitoring	Reliability for long-term maintenance of new technology.
Critical material use	As a cross-cutting of several issues, the necessity to use toxic or conflict materials in R&I processes.
Cybersecurity, environmental crime	Criminals attack the environment-related data and use it to abuse water and energy supply or cause environmental disasters.
Dual use	Potential use of R&I results in security and defence purposes or vice versa.
Waste management	As a cross-cutting issue, environmental justice on wasteland and people who deal with waste.
Access to the resource	Related to "justice and equity", socioeconomic situation leads to unequal distribution of access to resources.

Social Lab 3:

Issue	Description
Cultural relationships dimension	Relationships with the environment is embedded in cultural traditions, norms, and practices. Different cultural groups have different values and attitudes towards environmental and climate ethics.
Instrumentalization potential	There is an ongoing discussion of using third-country national immigrants and asylum seekers for certain purposes, which may influence environmental and climate justice.
Resettlement, migration, displacement, mobility	People living in places vulnerable to climate change are forced to migrate to different locations.

Social Lab 4:

Issue	Description
Epistemic Justice	Epistemic justice focuses on ensuring equity in the creation, sharing, and use of knowledge, while also fostering more inclusive knowledge generation and enhancing the credibility of underrepresented voices.
Intersectionality	Inequalities and injustice are multiplied and accumulated through individual's identity e.g., gender, race, social class

Social Lab 5:

Issue	Description
Access to Participation	Participation opportunity defers to individual with different backgrounds.
Resistance to Change	Some people might have negative idea and attitude towards changing the status quo.

Social Lab 6:

Issue	Description
Resilience	Resilience is becoming more important e.g. for forest ecosystems: It would be a good principle to increase the resilience of an ecosystem with one's research without harming it. Not only about the direct impacts but also about long term developments.
Governance/bureaucracy	The structures and processes through which decisions are made and implemented, often influencing environmental policies and practices.
Personal data / data integrity	The ethical management and protection of individual data to ensure accuracy, privacy, and security in research.
Communication	The effective exchange of information and ideas to foster understanding and collaboration in environmental research and innovation.
Social-Ecological relations and knowledge	The interconnected understanding of human societies and natural ecosystems, emphasizing the co-evolution of social and ecological systems.

Social Lab 7:

Issue	Description
Balance between economic incentives and technological advancement	As a cross-cutting issue, the participants highlighted the critical need for the balance between economic incentives and technological advancement for environmental sustainability.

Social Lab 8:

Issue	Description
Decision-making process	The priorities in the decision-making process - who makes decisions and with what intention and ideology. In other words, whose vision matters?
Public participation/ FPIC	Public participation for the decision-making process. Consultation based on FPIC (free, prior and informed consent).
Governance and knowledge	Knowledge holders that inform governance processes.
Indigenous historic land ownership	Consideration of indigenous historical land ownership and other land based on injustices that result from climate interventions.
Epistemic justice	The fair and equitable recognition and inclusion of diverse knowledge systems and perspectives in research and decision-making processes.
Role of capitalism	The influence of market-driven economic systems on environmental practices, policies, and the distribution of resources. (e.g., monetization of nature).
Indigenous knowledge systems/ traditional environmental knowledge	The valuable insights and practices developed by indigenous communities over generations, emphasizing sustainable and harmonious interactions with the environment.

4.3.2 Participant elaboration of climate and environmental ethics and integrity issues in R&I

After the plenary exercise participants were asked to share short stories related to the presented issues or additional issues, based on their own personal experiences. We framed the instruction of the exercise to be easily understandable and accessible – “Write the story as if you were telling it to a friend working in a different field”. This allowed us to collect stories that are not too technical while encouraging people to connect the issues with their practices. The following section shows examples of stories related to each issue, from different labs. Note that in some cases, *country, topic, org type* are not reported for quotations owing to inability to trace comments further in certain social labs.

Issue 1: Resource use/intensity

Some participants across the SLs addressed complex relationships between resource use and research practices. This includes the difficulties to implement comparative and holistic measures across different fields and sectors. Some problematised the energy use of computations and algorithms, particularly by major industry players.

"In research funding it may be difficult to evaluate potential emission cuts across fields, as some fields may require energy-intense machines, while others 'only' require travels (e.g. for field studies). Finding a balance that is fair to all disciplines is tricky." – SL1 # 12,

"Especially in agricultural applied research we face the challenge of a vast amount of research being done by agricultural industry players. It's very time and resource consuming to prove/deny the results achieved by industrial players. This is being fuelled by the upcoming of different algorithm/software applications on the same data sources with different outputs." – SL6, Germany, Agriculture, CSO

"Mr. [anonymised name] pointed out that as research advances, the consumption of computational resources is increasing rapidly, highlighting the need to develop sustainable computational infrastructure. He emphasized that the energy usage associated with high-performance computing should be considered a matter of ethical concern in research." – SL7

Issue 2: Technoeconomic challenges

Many participants addressed this issue at structural and systematic levels. Since it is difficult to address this issue at the individual or even sector level due to financial and societal constraints, the need for a policy framework was also suggested.

"Mr. [anonymised name] emphasized that for the adoption of smart agriculture technologies to be economically sustainable, support for small-scale farmers is essential. He stated that beyond technological advancement, a robust social framework is needed to sustain and operate these innovations effectively." – SL7

"During my research I am astonished by the slow adoption of technologies that could effectively promote and implement the "green" transition of our societies. ... Of course, there are economic reasons. For example, consume less, design for last, and transition to a circular economy is often at odds with the engrained capitalist views of our societies. However, other are more surprising including the lack of knowledge on the civil society and industrial agents about advanced green technologies or practices developed in a scientific setting. Moreover, within academia I feel that we are still miles away from true inter or even transdisciplinarity. Each discipline often lives in its own corner and have a hard time to bridge. Probably, also a result of an increasing performance-oriented culture in academia. It seems that we lost the insight of looking to the past. Often, I find redundant recent research that was done in the past and sometimes better than the one done nowadays. Also, a result of the current performance-driven culture of academia. All of this is preventing dissemination and implementation of very useful technologies and technical/scientific development. " – SL4, Denmark, Architecture/Building Simulation, HEI

Issue 3: Competing needs and priorities

Many participants reflected on this issue with their experience in the areas of energy systems, waste management, regional development, and agriculture. Tensions addressed ranged from geopolitical issues and economic interests to scalability, academic performance needs, agenda settings and distribution of funding.

“Working on distributed energy systems there is a difficult trade-off between being an opener for more inclusive energy transition (+access), but at the same time has costs to those who cannot engage as grid costs increase. ” – SL4, Norway, Human geography/Energy transition, RTO

“... As we have no time to waste, I feel that researchers are often too focused on writing nice publications than generating results that can be easily utilised by industry. We should use the limited research funding wisely. I do not say that basic research should not be done. We, however, could focus a bit more on the scalability topics in our research. Or at least keep that in mind.” – SL4, Finland, Batteries, RTO

“We need more funding for military sector than for climate sector because of the geopolitical situation in Europe. “– SL6, Germany, Bioeconomy, CSO

“we find that there is a disparity in the kinds of research being funded - often in the case of agriculture it is largely weighted towards corporate funding so already before research is designed there is often a bias in the focus of the research and prioritising the agenda of some over others - for example when we try to show that agroecology can be effective and provide food security and reduce environmental and climate impacts there is less funding for this, could it be necessary that different types of research would need to be considered” – SL 6, South Africa, Bioeconomy, HEI

Issue 4: Environmental impact

Environmental impact was also a well discussed issue. Participants shared stories of a variety of environmental impact: energy usage, waste, recyclability, repairability, genetically modified contamination, radioactive contamination. The discussions also covered difficulty of environmental impact assessment and measurement on long-term consequence, complex environmental problems and systems.

“In a research ethics course with PhD students they asked how they could evaluate environmental impact of AI use in their field. Seems that there are no easy available tools for that.” – SL1

“We organize a repair event every single month and we always have an equipment that it's not repairable, meaning the brand designed it in a way that makes very difficult to repair things. This is an example of obsolescence.” – SL2, Portugal, Circular economy, CSO

“Small-scale farmers in [location] have found GM contamination in their maize crop. Their maize varieties have been saved and selected for generations.” - SL6, South Africa, bioeconomy, HEI

“Mr. [anonymised name] pointed out that the decommissioning of nuclear power plants presents long-term environmental challenges. He noted in particular the ongoing difficulties in reaching consensus on the disposal of radioactive waste, emphasizing the need to seek sustainable solutions.” – SL7

Issue 5: Justice and equity

This issue was addressed in various dimensions: global south/north, urban/rural, settler/indigenous people, large corporation/SMEs, and upstream/downstream habitants. Many

pointed out that justice and equity cannot only be addressed in inclusion for the participation, but also structural problems such as priority setting or unconscious decisions. A participant also problematised “tick-box” style engagement as requirement for fundings.

“Working on an EU project aiming to involve “local stakeholders” in a consistent group to engage them on climate-related issues in their region (across different EU countries). In one of those regions lives a historically marginalised community, who EU project partners wanted to involve but they were not interested. EU project tried to involve a formal representative of the community - also wasn't interested. EU project gave up, thinking they tried everything.” – SL1

“During my environmental law studies, we were tasked to solve a hypothetical energy emergency scenario in [a country]. Our group refused to consider the construction of wind parks on [a minority's territory]. When receiving feedback, we were told that we did not provide sufficient arguments.” – SL3, Germany, Climate & Environmental Justice and Citizen Science, CSO

“On the research topic of carbon farming to store carbon dioxide in the soil through various technological solutions we found that research was often based on depleted or low maintenance soils. It's quite a challenge to make choice makers aware of local scopes in contrast to the global scope concerning the different climate areas we have. If the research is not broad enough, we face challenges in justice and equity.” - SL6, Germany, Agriculture, CSO

Issue 6: Impacts of technologies on animals

No participant stories were shared or collected on this topic.

Issue 7: Resource use in research practice

Only one participant addressed this issue in the workshop. This participant shared their experience on research in material science that required resources but did not show a positive result. They ended up switching the topic considering the impact of continuing the research.

“How much ‘good’ does a researcher have to do in order to offset harm done by their research? ... The work that I was doing was producing material that wasn't working that well, and I despaired with the balance between continuing this research which felt dead-end and switching to a different topic. Another part of research is conferences, and I felt that these materials were not good enough to be talked about or worth the time and investment to go to conferences. Knowledge that they don't work so well is also valuable, but is it worth the taxpayer money and the inherent harm in supporting these systems of extraction to find that out? ...” – SL4, UK, Batteries/Energy Storage, HEI

Issue 8: Gender dimension

Gender dimension was often talked with very specific examples the participants experienced. The stories show that gender dimension is based on structural inequalities through the cultural and social setting, which is difficult to tackle as individuals and, therefore, requires structural and infrastructural support through governance, regulations, and other mechanisms.

“The systematic and historical imbalance between genders in the field. vs. competence for individual projects. Imposing EU's HR requirements on an individual person is not fair, considering competing interests (e.g., project goal). However, this might be the only way to change the systematic gender imbalance... (chicken-or-the-egg problem)” -SL2, Luxembourg, Material science, RTO

“I would like to focus on a recent case study that addresses the gendered dimension of energy transitions. This also cuts across epistemic justice and intersectional aspects. [Anonymised name of project] turned women's knowledge in managing household energy to be a useful resource for the community-making them providers of critical care related infrastructure to the community. It also explains how in the process this altered gendered norms and power structures- and how transitions became an opportunity to address gendered injustices. There is also an important message here around active role of the state as provider of care related infrastructural support.” - SL4, Sweden, Just transition/Climate justice, HEI

“Water insecurity is experienced through social systems. One of these is gender. Gender can be thought of as a social process that gives people certain social positions, access, and roles. ... As a mother and wife, [anonymised name] had a responsibility to get water for her family, and to conserve water in cooking and cleaning. Despite this heavy responsibility, she did not have any role in community water governance—only men participated in the water committee. While [anonymised name] experienced household water insecurity as stressful, her husband experienced his governance and income-earning duties as a burden. This illustrates how, in different societies, gender positions give people different environmental responsibilities, worries, and problems.” – SL5, USA, Water Insecurity, HEI

4.3.3 Participant perspectives on causes underneath the issues

In this exercise, we asked the participants to deeply and widely explore the reasons under the issues we presented before. For this, we utilized role-playing style breakout sessions (Figure 9: Exercise on "Underlying whys"). The role division between "interviewer", "interviewee", and "note-taker" was designed to allow the participants to engage with the topics in a dialogue and, by doing so, reflect deeply with the issues while giving equal opportunities to all the participants to share their thoughts. While some groups followed the instructions to choose the issue and focused on the reasons of that issue, many groups intentionally or unintentionally focused their discussions on specific topics that were not directly related to the issues. Additionally, many groups discussed normative theses including policy reformulation and system change, tending toward a solution-oriented approach rather than open inquiry. SLB did not performed this exercise according to the (modification) plan.

The analysis involved grounded theory-led qualitative coding method on the workshop data.

Figure 9: Exercise on "Underlying whys"

The AIT team created topical codes on the participants' comments across the SLs, which were later consolidated based on the commonalities. The result supports the previous finding on the Issues (section 3.2) and reveals additional dimensions on environmental and climate ethics in R&I practices.

The exercise brought to light a range of systemic challenges and root causes participants perceived as contributing to the climate and environmental ethics issues presented. These discussions revealed that such issues are not isolated incidents but are deeply interconnected, shaped by the broader structures and systems that influence research agendas and decision-making processes.

Workshop discussions consistently underscored the difficulty of balancing competing priorities—such as economic imperatives, environmental sustainability, technological advancement, and social justice. Participants emphasised that these tensions are embedded within institutional frameworks, making ethical decision-making particularly complex.

A recurring theme across the sessions was the critical importance of interdisciplinary collaboration. Participants stressed that addressing ethical challenges requires bridging disciplinary and sectoral divides. They also highlighted the necessity of fostering inclusivity and epistemic justice to ensure that diverse perspectives and knowledge systems are genuinely integrated into research and policy development.

Another key outcome of the workshops was a strong call for enhanced governance and policy frameworks. Participants argued that without systemic reforms in research funding, evaluation criteria, and institutional priorities, it will be difficult to create the enabling conditions for innovations that are both sustainable and socially just. The workshops demonstrated that participatory methods and collaborative dialogue can foster ethical reflexivity, empowering individuals to critically examine their roles and responsibilities within these systems.

Ultimately, the findings from the workshops emphasized that practical solutions alone are insufficient. Creating an ethical, inclusive, and sustainable research environment requires transformative changes in governance structures, funding mechanisms, institutional cultures, and collaborative practices—anchored by a shared commitment to justice, equity, and sustainability.

The following are the causes which participants addressed. These causes are not mutually exclusive but rather complementary and/or synergistic. Group numbers reference the fact that small group discussions were used in the activity, within social labs.

Why 1: Competing needs and priorities

This well discussed topic considers conflicting needs, interests, and priorities, as already addressed in the interviews. Actors involved in the situation often have different values, interests, goals, and agendas that do not align with other actors. The participants shared many aspects that cause conflicts: short-term vs. long-term benefit, economic benefit vs. social and ecological benefit, bigger scale agenda vs. small local needs, etc.

“Utilitarianism for locals vs. ecosystem preservation considerations (usually coming from the outside, environmental scientists, conservationists)” – SL3 Group 3

“Of the three points which is the most important? Ethic considerations; representativeness, democratization” – SL5 Group 2

“Energy policy frameworks often overlook community needs and lived experiences.” - SL7 Group 1

Why 2: Silos/biases

Divisions and separation among discipline, organisations, sectors, professions (policymakers, researchers, business), social groups (age, economic and social status), etc. contribute to epistemic biases for identification of problems, agenda setting, selection of options, and decision making.

“Pressure lies on the seniors: they can't provide answers, and they are supposed to have the leading/guiding role; juniors are more agile, adaptable and (sometimes) have more experience/knowledge on new and emerging technologies” – SL1 Group 2

“Why this mismatch (between problem itself and scientific approach) is a problem: if you ask younger scientists, they simply don't recognize the issue. They haven't come across the actual problem in reality, and they take the issues from the literature, without backing it with their own empirical research.” – SL4 Group 1

Why 3: Epistemic injustice

Related to silos, some groups and individuals are particularly underrepresented or underprivileged to see and know issues.

“Declaration on the ethical principles on climate change. Who is producing and who is suffering. North / South, rural/urban.” – SL1 Group 1

“Equity - uneven distribution of moral idea of the fact that given cost should bring benefits for everyone” – SL3 Group 1

“if there is no access to data - or if it is presented in a way that is not understandable for everyone involved in the decision making process” – SL3 Group 1

“Sustainability in agriculture has a lot of indicators and underlying sets of indicators. Recipients of research are often very restricted. Research either remains too superficial or is too specialized.” – SL6 Group 3

Why 4: Decision-making process

Many participants identified problems in decision-making processes. Decision-making in agenda setting, policymaking, funding/subsidy allocation, or so, is heavily influenced by biases and access to information and knowledge. Decision-makers often face challenges of conflicting interests and thus prioritise certain goals. What to count in decision-makings shapes the directions of the consequences.

“The framing of environmental questions is often influenced by political and economic agendas.” – SL7 Group 1

“Temporal uneven distribution of burdens and benefits - policymakers cannot take decisions for future generations/responsibility” – SL3 Group 1

“Centralized/top-down decision-making processes, not democratic, no co-production of decision-making with other societal sectors. Single agenda approach.” – SL3 Group 1

Why 5: Lack of participation

Many participants addressed the needs for stakeholder involvement in decision-making processes. Participation in decision-making were often seen important for better alignment among stakeholders and effective outcomes. Formats of participation were also discussed.

“Possible solution: provide advance tools to monitoring. Involve tech and citizens in the projects. Harmonization between national policies. sanitary organizations. All value chain must be involved in projection and decision making.” – SL2 Group 2

“People affected may not have time or opportunity to speak up” – SL3 Group 2

“There are not that many energy communities. New regulations are coming though about this. Some communities do exist and they can make democratic decisions. It is inclusive within some communities, but not for everyone. Very little attention to people (e.g. in white papers), only to the technologies. Data can be also misused.” – SL4 Group 3

Why 6: Communication issue

Especially in SL6, the participants identified issues on communication that contribute to misunderstanding of information, wrong decision-making, and further conflicts.

“Native trees are usually advised to be preferred. But in the field, this is not the case b/c local population chose other species for the benefits and were not shown/communicated about the possible negative consequences of this choice” – SL3 Group 3

“Land-use conflict arise from lack of communication concerning stakes and interests (Olympic game, ecological impact, etc.); lack of trust” – SL6 Group 1

“Situation: blind-boxing - one cannot get active without knowing what the other intends” – SL6 Group 1

“Communication: It's easy to get lost in the issues and get desperate. People need to understand their own affectedness” – SL6 Group 3

Why 7: Lack of governance

Some participants pointed out that there are lack of regulations, standards, and frameworks in many phases in value chains. The governance discussions included from funding, policies, guidelines, to standards.

“Standardization and design for repairability would be a solution” – SL2 Group 1

“Quality control of data used for the decision taken + standard reporting processes can be compromised - credibility of reporting” – SL3 Group 1

“Increasing inequality leads to a rise of populist politicians which leads to a cut of funding to sustainable (env and climate) research” – SL3 Group 3

“Energy transition is a policy and governance issue. Agendas are set by research councils, political decision” – SL4 Group 1

“Governance barrier- absence of long-term political vision. tech support for politicians, governments should put this into the agenda. There might be increasing research calls on this issue (wind turbine decommission)” – SL4 Group 2

“It's a funding issue. How is data being generated? No transregional funding; need for transregional guidelines. But there is no interest from various players.” – SL6 Group 3

Why 8: Structural problems in R&I

Particularly for R&I practices, the participants addressed structural issues that shape limitation of scope, methodologies, and impacts. Notably, SL4 participants used “projectification” (similar to projectisation) to identify the issues regarding funding schemes, project durations, continuity, administrative tasks, etc. That relates to needs for collaboration and interdisciplinary approach to overcome the problems listed above.

“Justice is on the agenda. Good thing is that there are more requirements for projects to take into account of gender etc. However, often this is just checking a box, and the actual work is not done properly - only at the title level, no engagement with stakeholders from immigrant populations etc. It is not understood how difficult it is to engage with stakeholders.” – SL4 Group 3

“Projectification stands in way of long-term societal development, and short term means that every new project loses resource from the others. Lack of engaged connection between lab and 'world out there” – SL4 Group 1

“KPIs call to account but doesn't capture the full picture particularly in social sciences. Numbers take out of context” -SL4 group 1

“Q1: Interdisciplinarity as a key obstacle for projects? A: People are being lost in the process. Setting is not helpful for everyone. Not everyone who pays for research benefits from it. Politics and research does not address substantial issues.” – SL6 Group 3

“Not enough interdisciplinary research” – SL 6 Group 3

Additional discussion elements

Other than the listed topics above, the participants mentioned social system (SL5 Group2), values and emotion (SL3, SL5, SL6) to address aspects of current climate and environmental ethics in relation to R&I. SL moderators reflect the whole discussions as follows.

SL1: The discussions evolved around the topic of inclusion, especially the inclusion of local people in field studies and experts in the respective fields. The participants urged for common guidelines, rules and a framework in relation to ethics and sustainability.

SL2: A few themes recurred related to needs of reliability and repairability; lack of standardization for repairability; Another theme related to levels of demand or lack of

competence advance viable alternatives for certain energy or raw material intensive artifacts or processes.

SL3: NA

SL4: Participants also discussed the connection between the requirements for accounting and quantification of project results, and the prevalence of projectification in R&I and related difficulties in interdisciplinarity

SL5: NA

SL6: Talking to each other seems to be a connecting element between all whys. In order to tackle environmental issues, people need to work together, especially policy and practitioners.

SL7: Participants identified the need for cross-sectoral collaboration to effectively address ethical challenges in environmental sustainability. Key takeaways included: The necessity of adopting a more inclusive definition of sustainability that accounts for cultural, ecological, and socioeconomic dimensions; The discrepancy between governmental policy initiatives and the realities experienced by local communities; The crucial role of academic institutions in promoting ethical research practices and fostering interdisciplinary dialogue on sustainability.

4.4 Discussion of Workshop 1 Results

As a succeeding activity to the interviews, WS1 focused on the familiarisation of the Social Lab methodology and exploration of issues in environment and climate ethics in relation to R&I. Overall, WS1 across the SLs confirmed and enriched the findings from the interviews. This is, of course, partially because there was a substantial overlap of the interviewees and the WS attendees. Yet, different methodologies and setting facilitated to refine the previous findings and discover new aspects. The ranking of the issues shows commonalities across the SLs: *Environmental impact, Justice and equity, and Competing needs and priorities* ranked high while *Impacts of technologies on animals* ranked low. One WS moderator pointed out that this lack might attribute to the absence of representatives from sectors that concern natural lives more directly. The additional issues addressed cross-cutting concerns and added nuances to SL specific themes, such as *Transparency and access to environmental data* and *Condition and health monitoring* from SL2, *Resettlement, migration, displacement, mobility* in SL3 and region-specific themes, such as *Indigenous historic land ownership* and *Indigenous knowledge systems/Traditional environmental knowledge* in SL8. Tother with the story-telling style exercises, this broadened and deepened our understanding of complexities of environmental and climate issues in R&I.

The “Underlying Whys” exercise, while derailing somewhat from its original task, still brought us valuable insights. Even though participants were asked to dig deep to the root causes of specific environmental and climate ethics issues, many discussions shifted toward potential solutions or broader systemic issues. As a result, the conversations did not always explore in detail the underlying causes as planned. Nevertheless, the exercise surfaced various perspectives of ethical challenges. Participants flagged several recurring structural and systemic factors—such as conflicting priorities, institutional and disciplinary biases, non-inclusive decision-making

processes, lack of meaningful participation, and outdated communication patterns—as key factors contributing to the ethical issues in research and innovation. We observed that this exercise allowed participants to realise the interconnectedness of the issues and their underlying causes.

The workshop discussions also emphasized the challenge of managing multiple, often conflicting priorities, such as balancing economic pressures with environmental protection, or technological innovation with justice and equity. Participants consistently stressed the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration to bridge gaps across disciplines and sectors, alongside the need for inclusivity and epistemic justice to ensure diverse voices and knowledge systems are truly heard and integrated into research and policy design. However, some participants also highlighted the cross-sectoral challenges arising from the growing trend of projectification—that is, the increasing reliance on short-term, outcome-driven projects, frequently shaped by key performance indicators (KPIs).

Overall, WSI participants were actively involved in the process and showed strong engagement throughout the exercises and discussions. The feedback collected also indicated a positive experience with the project overall, including the SL method, facilitation, and use of online tools. In SL 1, workshop moderators noted distinct differences in perspectives between participants from the private and public sectors. Representatives from the private sector tended to emphasise marketing strategies and the development of products aimed at promoting sustainability. In contrast, public sector participants primarily focused on issues related to inclusiveness, ethical concerns such as misuse and ethics dumping (export of unethical research practices from higher income to lower income contexts), and the corresponding need for regulatory frameworks at the European level and beyond. Other SL moderators did not see significant differences and commonalities between sectors and R&I areas.

Having revealed the issues and the causes of environmental and climate ethics in R&I practices, Workshop 2 aimed to clarify the systematic, institutional, and individual responsibilities for addressing these challenges and to introduce the European Union's Green Transition Goals as strategic countermeasures.

5 Social Lab Workshop 2

Social Lab Workshop 2 aimed at exploring different perspectives on the EU Green Deal and participants' ideas for responding to the environmental and climate ethics and integrity issues surfaced in Workshop 1. As reported in the Social Lab Manual, Workshop 2 content supplemented the activities of Task 1.2: Analyse research ethics and integrity challenges of technologies and policies supporting the green transition, led by UT (02.01.2024–31.05.2025).

All the workshops were conducted online, except for the University of Tokyo Lab. For the half-day online workshops, we used the online digital whiteboard "[Mural](#)" for collaborative and interactive work. The University of Tokyo Lab used adopted and printed versions of the same workshop format for the in-person workshop. The workshops were conducted from December 2024 to mid-April 2025 across the SLs. Workshop 2 lasted 4 hours and was held online. The 4 hours were divided into two 90-minute sessions, each with a 10-minute break, and 60-minutes break for lunch half-way through.

5.1 Aims and scope

After an ice breaker to welcome any new participants, the first session of WS 1 focused on introducing goals of the EU Green Deal. The EU Green Deal Goals were presented as follows (in some labs, this information was presented in advance):

Clean, affordable, and secure energy. With [Clean, Affordable, and Secure Energy](#), the EU aims to **decarbonise** the energy system by aiming to achieve "**net-zero** greenhouse gas emissions **by 2050**."

The key principles include:

- to prioritize **energy efficiency**
- to develop a power sector based largely on **renewable resources** (e.g., offshore wind and hydrogen)
- to secure **an affordable EU energy supply**
- and to have a **fully integrated, interconnected digitalised EU energy market**

Sustainable Industry and Circular Economy. By introducing the [European Industrial Strategy](#) and [Circular Economy Action Plan](#) the EU aims to "empower citizens, revitalise regions and have the best technologies" and to explore and create "**climate neutral**" **circular economy-friendly goods markets**

The key principles include:

- to boost the **decarbonisation** and **modernisation** of industries (especially, **carbon-intensive industries** such as steel and cement)
- to **reduce wastage** of materials: **reusable** and **recyclable** materials including textiles, construction, vehicles, **batteries**, electronics and plastics
- to aim **stopping exporting waste** outside of the EU

Sustainable Living (Building and Renovation). With [Renovation Wave Strategy](#), the EU is targeting the process of building and renovation in regard to their **currently unsustainable methods**, and is **promoting sustainable living**

The key principles include:

- to promote the use of **energy-efficient building methods** such as climate-proofing buildings
- to increase **digitalisation** and **enforce rules** surrounding **the energy performance** of buildings
- to triple the renovation rate of all buildings to **reduce pollution**
- To promote social housing renovation, smart city mobility, environmental monitoring, and catastrophe prediction (e.g., [New European Bauhaus](#))

Safer and More Sustainable Chemicals. Chemicals are essential for modern living, but their production and use can pose **risks to human health and the environment**. The [EU Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability](#), adopted in March 2021, outlines a long-term vision for **a safer and more sustainable chemical industry**.

Key goals include:

- Enhanced **protection of human health**.
- Strengthening **industry competitiveness**.
- Supporting **a toxic-free environment**.

Sustainable Food Production. The [Farm to Fork Strategy](#) pursues the issue of food sustainability and the support to the producers, i.e. farmers and fishermen. The methods of production and transfer of these resources are what the E.U. considers a **climate-friendly approach**, aiming to **increase efficiency** as well.

Targets by 2030 are:

- Making 25% of EU agriculture **organic**.
- Reduce by 50% the use of **pesticides**.
- Reduce the use of **fertilizers** by 20%.
- Reduce **nutrient depletion** by at least 50%.
- Reduce the use of **antimicrobials** in agriculture and **antimicrobials** in aquaculture by 50%.
- Create **sustainable food labeling**.
- Reduce **food waste** by 50%.

Eliminating Pollution. The '[Zero Pollution Action Plan](#)' aims to achieve **no pollution** from "**all sources**", **cleaning the air, water and soil by 2050**.

The targets include:

- improving **air quality** to reduce the number of premature deaths caused by air pollution by 55%;
- improving **water quality** by reducing **waste, plastic litter at sea** (by 50%) and **microplastics** released into the environment (by 30%);
- improving **soil quality** by reducing **nutrient losses** and **chemical pesticide** use by 50%;
- reducing by 25% the EU ecosystems where **air pollution** threatens biodiversity;

- reducing the share of people chronically disturbed by **transport noise** by 30%, and
- significantly reducing **waste** generation and by 50% **residual municipal waste**

Sustainable mobility. A comprehensive strategy "[Sustainable and Smart Mobility](#)" includes targets to make mobility "**sustainable**", "**smart**", and "**resilient**" by 2030-2050:

- to increase the adoption of **sustainable and alternative fuels** in **road, maritime, and air transport**
- to fix the **emission standards** for combustion engine vehicles
- to develop **smart traffic management systems and applications**
- to **alter freight delivery** methods with the preferred pathways being by land or water
- to increase **public transport alternations** to reduce **public congestion** and **pollution**
- to increase **electric charging ports** to encourage the purchase of **low-emission vehicles**
- to develop a single European **air traffic management system** to increase **safety, flight efficiency, and environmentally friendly** conditions

Climate adaptation. Recognizing the **inevitability** of some climate change impacts, the [EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change](#) focuses on building a **climate-resilient Europe** by 2050.

Key areas of action include:

- Enhanced **data collection and sharing**: improved access to and exchange of knowledge on climate impacts for effective adaptation strategies.
- **Nature-based solutions**: the use of nature-based solutions to help climate resilience and protect ecosystems.
- Integration of adaptation into **macro-fiscal policies**: incorporating adaptation considerations into broader economic and fiscal planning.

Restore biodiversity. [EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030](#) tackles the critical issue of biodiversity loss in Europe, aiming to achieve a reversal by 2030.

Key actions within this strategy include:

- Expanding **protected land and sea areas**.
- **Restoring** degraded ecosystems by reducing pesticide use, including **forest restorations**.
- Increased **funding and monitoring**.

Just transition. [A Just Transition Mechanism](#): The transition to a low-carbon economy will vary in difficulty across EU member states and regions. Some regions are heavily reliant on fossil fuels or carbon-intensive industries, potentially facing **significant social and economic challenges** during the transition. The EU provides financial and technical

support (€55 billion mobilisation over the period 2021-2027) to address the concern focusing on:

- **People and communities:** facilitating **job creation** and **reskilling** initiatives, improving **energy efficiency in housing**, and combating **energy poverty**.
- **Companies:** making a shift to **low-carbon technologies** more financially attractive. Financial support and fosters investment in **R&I**.
- **Member states or regions:** investing in **new green jobs, sustainable public transport, digital connectivity**, and **clean energy** infrastructure

After being presented with these goals, participants were invited to share their impressions of whether they see the work in their field advancing or hindering EU Green Deal goals (Figure 10). Participants were explicitly notified this was being conducted as a non-judgmental exercise, with results reported anonymously, the point being to get to better understand tensions involved with R&I work for the green transition. To go deeper into these tensions, an individual exercise followed inviting participants to share specific stories elaborating “How does your work advance / hinder Green Transition Goals? Focus on your specific role and duties where possible. If not possible, talk about your field.”

Figure 10: Workshop 2, session on advancing / hindering EU Green Deal Goals, completed and with additional notes from subsequent conversation.

In the second focused session of the workshop, participants delved further into addressing climate and environmental ethics and integrity issues in R&I. The activity unfolded in three parts. First, participants were randomly divided into small groups and assigned or invited to pick 2 of the climate and environmental ethics issues from Workshop 1. Second, participants in the groups brainstormed ideas individually, related to a specific issue. Third, participants were asked “At what level of action might these ideas make the most sense to pursue”:

- Individual – actions they can affect directly.
- Organization / institution – actions one might take to effect change in one’s organization
- Field / profession – actions one might take to effect change in one’s field
- National – actions one might take to effect change in National policy or guidelines or organizing to effect change
- International – “” in international policy or guidelines or organizing to effect change
- (other) – a side sphere for other types of agency one feels they have / lack.

Participants were then facilitated to distribute their ideas to the different levels (Figure 11) in a diagram used as a discussion object.

Figure 11: Workshop 2 agency exercise, completed on Mural, with ideas in response to issues distributed across levels from individual to international and other.

The third and final activity involved asking participants to once again reflect on the allocated ideas, and answer, “When thinking about different phases of research and innovation, when might the opportunities discussed in Session 2 be realized or most appropriate?” Facilitators annotated each idea indicating whether the ideas might be implemented:

- Before project implementation, including: development of research agendas; calls for research; development of proposals; evaluation of proposals;
- During project implementation, including: team management and operations; data collection; data analysis; project evaluations (mid-term or final) outreach and engagement
- After project implementation, including: further exploitation of result; further development of technology; commercialization
- Alongside projects / independent / other, including: conference and workshop attendance; external advising; project developing technical standards; developing guidelines,

Where Social Labs had additional time, the discussions turned not only to when, but also how feasible the ideas might be, and what might be needed to resource the responses when. The workshop closed with a short discussion of outcomes that the participants would consider useful, logistics updates on Workshops 3 and 4, and an anonymous evaluation regarding workshop organization, facilitation, mural design, and other comments or feedback.

5.2 Participation

To expand the coverage of participation for WS2, we recruited additional stakeholders outside of the interviewees and WS1 participants. All workshops were conducted with informed consent of participants in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation, EU Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR), using a consent form (Annex 1) reviewed and approved by the German Reference Centre for Ethics in the Life Sciences. The Research Ethics Committee at UAB requested minor modifications to the Consent Form in accordance with current participatory research standards, resulting in the necessary ethics approval. AU applied for ethics approval for SL4 for the study RE4GREEN, Social Lab on Energy, and it was approved by the Institutional Review Board at Aarhus University, approval no. BSS-2024-098-L.

A total 45 participants across the SLs participated in WS2. The decrease in total number reflects the fact that one international partner lab did not take place as planned in this 1st implementation period; and select participants cancelling attendance at the last minute due to unforeseen circumstances. The gender distribution of participants included 24 females and 21 males. Participation by sectors were research performing (60%), civil society and media (11%), public sector including funders and research ethics committees (11%), private sector (9%), and other (9%) (Figure 12 on sector and Figure 13 on geographic distributions).

Figure 12: Participation by sector in WS2

Figure 13: Geographical distribution of WS2 participants. Austria: 3, Latvia: 2, Portugal: 1, Spain: 6, Switzerland: 2, Belgium: 2, Czech Republic: 1, Germany: 7, Luxembourg: 1, Greece: 1, Netherlands: 2, Finland: 2, Norway: 2, Ireland: 1, UK: 2, Denmark: 2, Chile: 2, USA: 1, South Korea: 1, Japan: 4, Kazakhstan: 1. (If the participants have double affiliations or their organisations have multiple locations, we counted all of them.)

5.3 Results

5.3.1 Relationship to EU Green Transition Goals

Figure 14: Relationships to the EU Green Transition Goals

In this exercise, we explored relationship and tensions between the participants' work and the EU Green Transition (GT) Goals. After the moderator's brief explanation on the 10 EU GT Goals that we identified, the participants were asked to indicate if the work in their fields "definitely advances", "slightly advances", "slightly hinders", "actually hinders" each goal. The consolidated result of all SLs (except for SL3, SL7, and SL8, where the exercise was not facilitated) shows diverse relationships between R&I practices and GT Goals, b) "Sustainable Industry and Circular Economy" had the most votes of "definitely advance" followed by "e) Sustainable Food Production," i) Restore Biodiversity," h) Climate Adaptation", and "j) Just Transition". Meanwhile, "slightly advance" was indicated the most for "d) Safer and More Sustainable Chemicals", "a) Clean, Affordable, and Secure Energy", "f) Eliminating Pollution", and "Restore Biodiversity". "c) Sustainable Living" and "g) Sustainable Mobility" were the least mentioned as been advanced by their work. On the other hand, the participants did not considerably address tensions between their work and GT Goals. No participants indicated that their works "actually hinder" GT Goals. Some participants addressed that their work "slightly hinder" "f) Eliminating Pollution", "i) Restore Biodiversity", "g) Sustainable Mobility", "d) Safer and More Sustainable Chemicals, and "j) Just Transition". Some participants shared their work had ambivalent impacts, i.e., their work both advances and hinders GT Goals.

To summarize, the workshop participants provided a diverse range of insights on the ways their work both advances and hinders progress toward broader Green Transition objectives. On the advancing side, they highlighted efforts such as fostering innovation, education, and collaboration across sectors. Participants shared how they are driving sustainability through improved policies, technological solutions, circular processes, community engagement, and enhanced data and knowledge sharing. They emphasized the importance of integrating sustainability into daily practices, promoting inclusivity, and engaging a wide range of stakeholders. Additionally, many noted their contributions to fostering green skills, raising awareness, and encouraging behavioral change.

However, participants also acknowledged factors from their work that hinders the GT goals. These included structural barriers that reinforce existing unsustainable practices, technological and resource constraints, and the environmental trade-offs associated with new solutions. Concerns were raised about the social and environmental costs of large-scale transitions, including increased energy demands, persistent reliance on harmful materials, and the complexity of balancing multiple goals. Funding limitations, slow adoption of innovations, and resistance to change were also seen as obstacles. Across all discussions, the need for systemic thinking, radical innovation, and careful management of competing priorities emerged as essential for overcoming these challenges and realizing a just and sustainable Green Transition.

The following section presents a summary of participants' discussions on how their work contributes to or hinders progress toward each of the Green Transition goals. Full responses are noted in Annex 3 – Workshops 2 responses relating to the GT

Clean, affordable, and secure energy **Advancing**

Participants mentioned their work on education and workforce development for the energy sector, including the preparation of the next generation of engineers and scientists. There was a strong sense of support for materials innovation to boost energy efficiency and renewable technology performance. Initiatives to expand renewable energy, such as improving grid infrastructure and integrating onshore and offshore wind and solar power, were highlighted. Policy and regulatory advancements, community engagement and capacity building were also highlighted as contributions to the energy transition, alongside efforts to sharing best practices and working on sustainability assessments.

Hindering

Hindering factors for this goal include the resource-intensity of research itself and slow technology transfer. Another challenge is that negative assessments of the technical or economic feasibility of certain technologies can sometimes be interpreted as suggesting that the entire energy transition is unfeasible, leading to hindering this goal. Concerns were expressed about the environmental trade-offs of renewable infrastructure, including potential habitat disruption and ecological fragmentation. Participants noted the difficulty of balancing energy transition goals with economic growth and job creation, and the insufficient critical engagement with environmental impacts of renewables. The high carbon footprint of

international meetings and the increased energy demand driven by digitization were also seen as hindering factors for this goal.

Sustainable Industry and Circular Economy

Advancing

Participants shared their efforts that advance sustainable industry and circular economy through funding foundational research, supporting circular processes and biorefineries, and promoting reuse, repair, and recycling practices. They highlighted work on bio-based technologies, residue valorization, and education to strengthen bioeconomy skills. Efforts also include helping green startups thrive, raising awareness of sustainability in industry, and developing communication strategies to shift consumer behavior.

Hindering

Hindering aspects included high resource and energy demands (e.g., in space and material sectors), risks in technology adoption, and consumer resistance to sustainable products. Participants mentioned conflicts between sustainability and economic priorities, greenwashing, and difficulties in sustainable communication. Reluctance to collaborate and increased travel needs for business were also seen as obstacles.

Sustainable Living (Building and Renovation)

Advancing

One participant shared efforts to promote sustainable living by educating municipalities and citizens on waste prevention and advocating for circular economy practices to reduce the amount of waste generated and managed.

Hindering

There were no hindering comments discussed during the workshops for this goal.

Safer and More Sustainable Chemicals

Advancing

Participants described work to advance safer and more sustainable chemicals by adopting environmental safety protocols, developing safer compounds (e.g., replacing synthetic surfactants with biosurfactants), and innovating safer processing methods to eliminate harmful chemicals.

Hindering

A key factor noted was the continued use of hazardous substances like fluorides and nickel, which remain difficult to replace in some processes.

Sustainable Food Production

Advancing

Participants mentioned their work on AI and smart technologies to improve precision in agriculture and enable reduced use of pesticides, fertilizers, and resources while increasing yields. They highlighted collaborations with farmers to develop nature-based solutions, promote biodiversity, and improve resilience. Other efforts included capacity-building programs, community-based management, and support for market integration of sustainable agriculture solutions.

Hindering

Negative contributions include high energy demands of AI systems, which may offset sustainability gains, and resistance from traditional farmers to adopting new technologies, which may limit widespread adoption.

Eliminating Pollution

Advancing

Participants shared their work on advancing pollution reduction by raising awareness among researchers about their environmental impact, adopting green research practices, and reducing travel through virtual tools. They highlighted awareness and cleanup efforts, ocean literacy education, and freshwater ecosystem restoration and conservation. Contributions include environmental modeling, nature-based solutions for wastewater, and the use of smart agricultural technologies to reduce overuse of inputs.

Hindering

Hindering factors include the CO2 footprint of funded research, travel-related emissions, and resource use in academia. Funding limitations and a focus on scientific excellence over environmental impact constrain progress. Limited applied research projects and continued reliance on printed materials were also cited as barriers.

Sustainable mobility

Advancing

Participants highlighted the crucial role of batteries in enabling electric mobility and efforts to reduce transportation emissions. They noted work on replacing critical raw materials with sustainable alternatives, developing low-energy and low-toxicity battery processing methods, and ensuring battery recycling solutions are in place.

Hindering

Factors that hinder the goal include the increased air pollution from heavier electric vehicles' tyres, environmental impacts of mining for raw materials, and the potential risks of deep-sea mining to meet battery demand. Concerns were also raised about the use of PFAS materials in batteries and the difficulty of finding suitable alternatives.

Climate adaptation

Responses were not presented for this goal.

Restore biodiversity

Advancing

Participants described efforts to restore biodiversity through bioremediation of soils and water, supporting data collection and sharing on climate and biodiversity impacts, and providing evidence for biodiversity conservation. They highlighted smart technologies for sustainable agriculture, agroecological approaches, and urban forests and agriculture as nature-based solutions. Contributions included global biodiversity assessments, bioeconomy promotion, and education on green transition challenges in forestry.

Hindering

Challenges include the prioritization of mineral extraction over environmental protection, the energy demand of digital tools for forest planning, and the risk of greenhouse gas emissions from scaling up restoration efforts. Participants also noted that incremental innovations may slow the needed radical changes.

Just transition

Advancing

Participants highlighted projects aimed at creating a fair, inclusive, and sustainable society, emphasizing the importance of including diverse voices in governance, and promoting community participation in water decision-making. Efforts also support regional transitions, cross-sector collaboration, and conceptual research to define what is just in sustainability transitions.

Hindering

Challenges include the tendency for solutions to reinforce existing structures, academic travel emissions, and overcomplicating processes, which can delay progress. Concerns were raised about automation's impact on employment and the slowing effect of multi-stakeholder negotiations.

5.3.2 Agency exercise

In this exercise, participants shared a wealth of ideas and insights to address climate and environmental ethics challenges in R&I, exploring actions that could be implemented at various levels—from individual to international. Discussions emphasized the need for both systemic and individual changes, such as adopting energy-saving behaviours, advancing sustainable technologies, fostering inclusivity, and promoting environmental stewardship. Participants

highlighted the importance of balancing technological progress with social and environmental priorities, pointing out that issues like resource intensity, technoeconomic barriers, competing needs, environmental impact, justice and equity, and the ethical treatment of animals require thoughtful, multi-level strategies. They recognized that institutions, professional communities, governments, and international collaborations all play vital roles in shaping sustainable practices and policies. The exercise revealed a strong desire for holistic, cross-sector approaches that integrate ethical considerations into decision-making processes, while also acknowledging the practical challenges—such as funding limitations, slow adoption of innovations, resistance to change, and systemic inequalities—that can hinder progress. The results gathered throughout the workshops is resented below as a summary of responses elaborated per issue per level.

Issue 1: Resource use/intensity

- **Individual:** Suggestions for individuals included adopting energy-saving measures at home and at work (e.g., switching to LEDs, regulating heating, using public transport), and being mindful of personal energy consumption in household appliances and daily routines.
- **Organization / Institutional:** Suggestions on the organizational level included the analysis and reduction of their energy use through data analysis and collaboration with other institutions. Recommendations for organizations included having clear institutional policies and regulations that align with national energy goals. Institutions could lead by example through sustainable energy initiatives, like adopting renewable technologies, having a carbon budget, using positive energy districts or community energy for their operations.
- **Field / Profession:** Participants emphasized the importance of changing the broader energy mindset within research-intensive industries. Encouraging low-energy production and industry-specific transitions was seen as key.
- **National:** On the national level it was suggested to update infrastructures for energy efficiency, fund upgrades for older buildings (like Soviet-era housing), and promote transparent, innovative strategies to reduce consumption in general. Suggestions included smart grid development, policies to cap energy use or re-purpose industrial waste streams amongst others.
- **International:** At the international level, participants proposed building infrastructure to support sustainable travel (e.g., EU-wide bullet trains), and enhancing global smart renewable energy networks. They also mentioned repurposing industrial waste streams and developing policies that support sustainable living on a transnational scale.
- **Other:** Additional suggestions noted challenges in applying sustainability thinking to real-world business and policy contexts. Review processes may undervalue environmental dimensions, and businesses often face barriers related to cost, feasibility, and timeline for tech adoption. A more holistic, less figure-focused approach was proposed to overcome these challenges.

Issue 2: Technoeconomic challenges

- **Individual:** At the individual level, addressing the lack of knowledge about green technologies was put forward. Suggestions included integrating applied ethics into education in all areas, improving understanding of alternative green technologies, and

making new technologies more accessible. Participants noted that people often default to familiar options due to unfamiliarity with or mistrust of greener choices.

- **Organization / Institutional:** Institutions could provide training and support for employees unfamiliar with green technologies. Structural and ethical considerations could be included in internal agendas. Suggestions also involved funding mechanisms for sustainable innovation and addressing the high costs of transition technologies like energy-efficient hardware.
- **Field / Profession:** Participants recommended enhancing science communication and education around energy efficiency and resource limitations of our planet. Professional communities were encouraged to address the stigma around industry being the problem by clearly communicating the pros and cons of technologies. Alternatives for costly systems (like space launches) and considerations of hardware exploitation costs (AI, computing) were emphasized, along with the need for skill training and initiatives for sustainable research infrastructures.
- **National:** Participants called for consistent long-term policies, reduced bureaucratic hurdles, and financial instruments like green loans to support the adoption of high-cost sustainable technologies. Participants emphasized clear regulatory frameworks and predictable planning on the national level.
- **International:** Suggestions included synchronizing regulations across countries and supporting international funding structures for clean technology. Challenges like migration for skilled labour and non-deployable research outputs were mentioned. Participants raised the issue of western views being imposed on other countries. The need for consistent and clear policy landscape was also mentioned.

Issue 3: Competing needs and priorities

- **Individual:** Participants pointed to everyday choices—like travel or car purchases—as opportunities to reconcile personal economic and environmental priorities. Sharing factual, accessible information through personal networks and professional platforms (e.g., LinkedIn) was emphasized.
- **Organization / Institutional:** NGOs and NPOs were highlighted as key actors, especially in rural areas, addressing tensions between profit motives and sustainable practices. Institutions can create internal guidelines and support interdisciplinary communication to manage conflicting objectives.
- **Field / Profession:** The role of professional media was highlighted for its ability to convey complex information in a digestible way. Opportunities for collaboration between scientists were noted to better engage the public.
- **National:** National policies can help mediate local conflicts (e.g., wind turbines in the backyard problem vs. community or indigenous priorities) and fund initiatives that balance conservation with development. Suggested actions included developing regulations and guidance to weigh environmental harm against technological progress, improving public engagement, for example through EU funding. Inclusive decision making was also emphasized.
- **International:** Respondents highlighted the importance of EU frameworks, specifically to create clear pathway on how to embed the green deal whilst also staying competitive and to evaluate results. Participants suggest the need for action for international regulation that accounts for environmental harm alongside technological advancement.

Issue 4: Environmental impact

- **Individual:** At the individual level, people should be given relatable examples and clear use cases to understand environmental issues. Participants also highlighted the importance of allowing researchers the time and support to apply their specialized knowledge to environmental challenges.
- **Organization / Institutional:** Institutions could contribute by offering applied examples, tailored to specific areas and supporting expert-led research and consulting. In contexts where possible, non-toxic and biodegradable materials should be used (in research and deployment). Institutions could also fund and promote environmentally beneficial technologies and play a more active role in public communication.
- **Field / Profession:** At the professional level, participants noted the importance of raising awareness of environmental issues as often the impacts are unknown, not talked about or justified for the sake of research. Collaborations across disciplines was also highlighted as an important factor.
- **National:** On the national level different mechanisms were suggested to address complex trade-offs like creating awareness and engaging stakeholders. There are examples how issues raised by local communities can reach the policy domain on the national level (e.g. how seabed mining was banned in Portugal).
- **International:** International action could focus on creating stronger environmental regulations and education efforts, especially in regions affected by resource depletion like mining and oil extraction. Participants called for EU and global policy frameworks to promote environmental impact assessments, science communication, and tools like unbiased technology assessment web platforms. Lobbying for eco-design and repair rights, and holistic evaluations of technology's true benefits or harms, were also suggested.

Issue 5: Justice and equity

- **Individual:** Suggestions at the individual level focused on increasing inclusivity through networking, outreach, and participation in initiatives that promote equality. Individuals should seek to integrate diverse perspectives into discussions and decisions (e.g., through inclusive projects and open calls).
- **Organization / Institutional:** Organizations were encouraged to implement continuous tracking of resource use to ensure transparency and accountability? (noting that there was very little data in this section)
- **Field / Profession:** Participants suggested establishing discipline-specific guidelines and systematically engaging in projects aimed at improving global equity—particularly North–South relations. This includes actively involving organizations from developing countries in research and collaboration efforts in the EU.
- **National:** National governments could develop more inclusive urban planning policies, such as creating blue and green spaces that bring natural benefits to all citizens. Strengthening governance systems to better incorporate diverse voices was also suggested as a step toward equity.
- **International:** International collaborations should further adopt the TRUST Code (Global Code of Conduct for Equitable Research Partnerships). Respondents emphasized involving diverse actors in debates—taking into account gender, age, culture, and geography.

Issue 6: Impacts of technologies on animals

- **Individual:** no representative information was given
- **Organization / Institutional:** Participants suggested that organization through internal policies could encourage the use of AI or other new emerging technologies like organoids instead of living animals.
- **Field / Profession:** On the professional level a specific recommendation was the reconceptualization of what wildlife means. This could offer a way forward in addressing challenges that are deeply rooted in the industrial agricultural practices and are harmful for animals.
- **National:** National-level suggestions focused on specific conflicts, such as how reindeer herding is negatively affected by wind turbines and mining. Participants advocated for adherence to international standards and for policies to be developed with the involvement of local communities.
- **International:** At the international level, participants called for robust debates on the ethical use of animals in research (3Rs), and better regulation of emerging technologies. They brought up the need for rules to prevent further biodiversity loss and protect habitats of species, such as those affected by palm oil production and deep-sea mining. Promoting plant-based diets was also proposed to lessen the use of animals in food systems.

Issue 7: Resource use in research practice

- **Individual:** It was suggested that researcher should reflect on their own resource use as part of their research process. Suggestions included raising more awareness of individual energy use and carbon footprint. Specific recommendations were combining field trips to reduce travel or use car sharing and trains whenever possible.
- **Organization / Institutional:** As for institutions, participants called for setting clear expectations and limits on resource use, providing CO2 budgets for travels and lab materials. Tracking the carbon footprint of conferences and projects was proposed as a way to measure and evaluate sustainable practices over time.
- **Field / Profession:** Participants suggested implementing sensible limits on resource use in research projects, such as those funded by Horizon Europe. Recommendations included developing ethical codes of conduct, promoting awareness of energy and material consumption (e.g., AI electricity use), and standardizing how research results are reported to avoid duplication. Clear guidelines would enable better cross-project comparisons and help identify gaps in existing research.
- **National:** National level suggestion for actions included supporting green energy use in research through medium and smaller providers and helping the economic burdens for using sustainable recourse. Using the EU Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive as a guiding framework for assessing environmental and social impacts of research projects was highlighted.
- **International:** On the international level the EU's Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive was mentioned again as a helpful guide. Including energy consumption criteria in funding calls and proposals was also emphasized.

Issue 8: Gender dimension

- **Individual:** Individuals were suggested to lead by example and share experiences, for example visiting schools to raise awareness about gender issues. The feedback highlighted that gender biases and discrimination are still pervasive in everyday life and that institutional responses often face skepticism. Although progress is being made, participants stated there is still a long road ahead without a clearly defined path.
- **Organization / Institutional:** On the institutional level suggestions included having more inclusive job openings, avoiding male dominance in panels and decision-making. Furthermore, inviting groups who work in the field of gender equality for collaborations was seen as a productive way forward.
- **Field / Profession:** Respondents suggested engaging professional associations to create opportunities specifically for women and marginalized groups and emphasized the significance of understanding local contexts to propose effective, realistic solutions.
- **National:** On the national level, however the input was brief, participants recommended that all actors should think critically about the issue.
- **International:** Similarly on the national level, the involvement of all actors in debates and discussions was emphasized.

5.4 Discussion of Workshop 2 Results

Workshop 2 of the project built upon the initial discussions of Workshop 1, but also offered participants the opportunity to explore how their work explicitly advances and hinders progress towards the EU Green Deal goals.

The workshop revealed that participants' work often contributes significantly to advancing sustainability goals. Across areas like clean energy, circular economy, sustainable food systems, pollution reduction, and biodiversity restoration, participants shared initiatives such as fostering collaboration, advancing green technologies, improving regulatory frameworks, and engaging with diverse stakeholders. They also described efforts to integrate sustainability principles into daily operations and decision-making processes, highlighting examples of stakeholder engagement projects, and policy advocacy.

At the same time, participants were invited to explicitly reflect on how their work might hinder Green Transition goals. These reflections revealed systemic challenges such as the environmental impacts of technological development, the carbon footprint of research activities (e.g., international travel, resource-intensive practices), and the persistence of unsustainable materials and methods in certain sectors. Participants recognized that their work could inadvertently reinforce existing unsustainable structures, contribute to social and environmental trade-offs, or slow progress through reliance on incremental changes rather than transformative innovation.

Specific concerns were raised about the mining of critical raw materials, the environmental costs of AI and digital technologies, and resistance to adopting new practices—particularly in sectors like traditional farming, chemical industries, and energy systems. Despite the conversation revealing multiple areas where participants' work might hinder Green Transition goals, few participants explicitly marked their work as “hindering” the transition. This could be because the hindering factors are nuanced, characterized by tensions, ambivalence, and

indirect barriers that may not always be fully visible. Perhaps these challenges remain unclear or unrecognized in participants' day-to-day practices.

The agency exercise generated ideas for overcoming the climate and environmental ethics issues from workshop 1 by identifying actions at multiple levels—individual, organizational, professional, national, and international. Participants proposed measures ranging from personal behavioral changes and institutional sustainability policies to systemic reforms such as clearer regulatory frameworks, funding mechanisms for green innovation, and international agreements for fair and sustainable practices. These discussions highlighted the need for holistic approaches that consider both technological progress and social justice, balancing short-term practicalities with long-term sustainability goals.

In summary, Workshop 2 offered a candid and multifaceted reflection on the dual role of participants' work in supporting and sometimes hindering the Green Transition. It emphasized the need for cross-sector collaboration, radical innovation, and inclusive governance to overcome persistent barriers. Looking forward, Workshop 3 is envisioned as an opportunity to focus on translating insights from these discussions into actionable strategies that bridge the gap between current practices and the ambition of a just and sustainable transition.

6 Discussion and Conclusions

Over the first year of implementation (May 2024–April 2025), the RE4GREEN Social Labs have engaged more than 120 researchers, practitioners, and stakeholders across eight labs to identify, validate, and deepen our understanding of climate and environmental ethics and research integrity issues in R&I. By conducting 124 interviews, and two rounds of participatory workshops, we have mapped out the key ethical issues, systemic barriers, and potential coping strategies that characterize the pursuit of a just and sustainable green transition. In this concluding section we summarize our findings with drawing connections to the results of the literature review (D.1.2) of WP1 and we outline the next steps of the social lab process.

The interviews uncovered a wide spectrum of climate and environmental ethics concerns connected to R&I. These issues, drawn from all eight Social Labs, reflect systemic tensions that cut across disciplinary, sectoral, and geographical lines.

In the first workshop, participants engaged in a collective exploration of the key issues identified during the interview phase, assessing their relevance and impact within their respective research and innovation contexts. Among the issues, *environmental impacts*—both from research activities and technological outputs—and *justice and equity* emerged as the most significant and widely shared concerns. Also considered highly relevant were the challenges of *resource intensity*, *technoeconomic constraints*, and *competing needs and priorities*, which often create tensions between innovation, sustainability, and social responsibility. While viewed as less prominent, issues such as the *gender dimension*, *resource use within research practices*, and the *impact of technologies on animals* were still acknowledged as important and deserving of further attention, especially within specific disciplinary or regional settings.

As part of the second workshop, we explored how stakeholders see themselves advancing or hindering green transition goals. In general, there was an overarching optimism and positive contribution highlighted, but this could well be due to the limited knowledge about the specifics of the green transition. In our further analysis we would like to link the explore issues and map their details to the green transition to get a clearer picture of the hindering aspect.

The findings of the interview and workshops conducted resonate with several key themes identified in the literature review (D 1.1) of WP1, including the centrality of justice, responsibility, and sustainability as cross-cutting concepts.

For instance, the justice and equity concerns raised by interviewees and workshop participants—such as resource use disparities, technoeconomic challenges, and the socio-economic inequalities of energy transitions—align closely with the academic emphasis on distributive, procedural, and recognition justice within environmental and climate ethics.

Environmental justice, for example, was found frequently cited in the literature review, emphasizing the importance of fairness in decision-making processes and acknowledging diverse experiences and pluralistic values of people. The workshops results also highlighted the need for inclusivity and interdisciplinary collaboration that mirrors this conceptual grounding and reinforces the call for participatory approaches to decision-making that were found in the literature.

The idea that environmental and climate ethics consideration should be embedded in both research practices and technologies is also emphasized in both the literature and empirical findings. For example, concerns over environmental impacts in sectors such as energy, digital technologies, and lab-based research—identified in interviews and workshops—reflect the literature’s observation of a research ethics and integrity gap regarding environmental impacts of research practices.

Additionally, the literature highlights epistemic justice, which calls for the recognition of diverse knowledge systems, including Indigenous and local knowledge, a concern also raised in workshop discussions. The participants’ emphasis on integrating diverse voices, particularly in regions with specific socio-environmental challenges, corresponds with calls in the literature for more inclusive and pluralistic approaches to knowledge production and governance.

The interviews and workshops provided rich and context-specific insights that extend beyond the coverage of the literature review, offering a nuanced view of environmental and climate ethics as experienced and enacted in practice. One important consideration that emerged was the recognition of tensions between technological innovation and minimizing environmental harm. Participants emphasized the challenges of balancing local needs with global goals.

Furthermore, Workshop 2 generated discussions about the ways in which current research and innovation practices can hinder the green transition. Participants highlighted the environmental impacts of AI, digital technologies, resource-intensive sectors, and high-carbon practices like academic travel. Despite their intentions to support sustainability, many participants recognized that their work could reinforce unsustainable structures and practices that currently exist.

Throughout the workshops, the need for cross-disciplinary collaboration became increasingly clear. Participants recognized that bridging disciplinary, institutional, and sectoral silos is essential for addressing the intertwined ethical and environmental challenges they face.

Another key conclusion from the workshops was the call for stronger governance and policy frameworks. Participants emphasized that without systemic changes in how research is funded, evaluated, and prioritized, it will be difficult to create the conditions needed for funding research and innovations that align with the green transition goals and addresses the related ethical issues. The workshops also demonstrated the potential for participatory approaches and collaborative dialogue to foster ethical reflexivity, enabling participants to reflect critically on their own roles, assumptions, and responsibilities.

6.1 Challenges and coping factors

The scope of this project was shaped by ambitious objectives, aiming to engage a broad spectrum of participants from diverse countries, sectors, and stakeholder groups. This inclusive approach successfully ensured representation of a wide array of voices and perspectives. However, it is important to note that the resulting data should not be interpreted as statistically representative of the whole European Research Area. Due to the extensive diversity across categories such as career levels, stakeholder groups, countries, and disciplines, we were unable to conduct extensive, representative, comparative analyses across these dimensions. Instead,

our findings are intended to identify areas warranting further exploration, validation, or discussion within the existing literature on environmental and climate issues in the context of research ethics and integrity. The findings also point out opportunities to creatively address climate and environmental ethics issues in R&I, and provide an insight into the level of awareness, generally, of these issues among researchers and other R&I stakeholders.

Recruitment posed a number of challenges, primarily due to budget constraints that limited us primarily to online workshops. While this format enabled broader geographic participation, it often proved less engaging than in-person workshops, where participants tend to be more immersed and interactive. Based on participant feedback indicating that the online sessions were overly long and mentally demanding (even at only 4 hours with 1.5 hours of lunch/break time built in), we have decided to shorten the third online workshop to a total duration of two hours.

The project requires a significant time commitment from participants—three online workshops and one in-person session—which is contributing to a higher rejection rate than initially anticipated. In the original use of social labs in the *NewHoRRizon* project, budget was available to conduct 3 in person 1.5-day workshops per 18 labs. Despite being more time intensive, the quality of in-person experience, opportunity to network and exchange in person, to delve more deeply at length into topics, may offer a recruitment edge to consider for future social-lab-based research. In the interim, to address this issue, in addition to reducing the time request in Workshop 3, we have made considerable efforts to recruit replacement participants whenever original invitees were unable to attend.

An additional challenge emerged from the involvement of international social labs based in South Africa and Japan. These labs operate within very different contexts compared to their European counterparts, particularly in relation to the European Green Deal. As a result, we had to adapt our methodology to accommodate these differences while remaining aligned with the overall goals of the project. Adjustments are being implemented to ensure meaningful contributions from these labs to the RE4GREEN project while also respecting the specific needs and expectations of their local communities and national policy environments. These methodological modifications, along with their outcomes, will be detailed in the Implementation Report 2.

The design of our workshops was uniquely tailored to the goals of the RE4GREEN project. As such, some exercises yielded mixed results. One key learning was the importance of more intensive facilitation during breakout sessions, particularly to ensure accurate notetaking. Additionally, we found that providing even more detailed instructions and concrete examples would help participants better understand and engage with the exercises. Higher level of detail also helps better assure consistent facilitation across the labs. These improvements will be implemented in future sessions. The "Underlying Whys" exercise in the first workshop was most impacted by these issues, as observed in the varying ways participants interpreted and responded to the activity.

A final point relates to our planned inclusion of citizen scientists. Initially, we intended to involve two citizen scientists per Social Lab. However, due to unresolved issues with the European Commission regarding their compensation, Citizen Scientists were not included in the interviews and the first two workshops. In the next phase of the Social Lab process, we will

address this gap by conducting interviews with the citizen scientists to either validate or refine our findings and they will also be involved in the upcoming workshops (having resolved uncertainties with the European Commission on compensation).

6.2 Next steps

The second phase of social lab implementation involves workshops 3 and 4. Workshop 3 will be a two-hour session discussing RE4GREEN draft guidelines and training materials designed to support the ERA community to consider and respond to climate and environmental ethics issues in R&I. To make up for the shorter time period allotted, advance materials will be provided to participants to review and attend ready to discuss. Workshop 4 will be an in-person 1.5-day event, delving into questions of “do no significant harm” and environmental risk assessment, as a policy and protocol for responding (in part) to climate and environmental search ethics and research integrity issues for the green transition.

After completion of implementation phases 1 and 2, additional analysis will be conducted across the labs, for example, digging more deeply into cross-issue responses to climate and environmental ethics issues. In addition further conversations will be conducted with the Work Package 1 team to identify complementary insights from the literature review, interviews, and participatory results of social lab workshops. Final conversations will also take place within each social labs about legacy and future collaborations among participants in general, and with topics of climate and environmental ethics and research integrity.

Annex 1 – Interview Consent Form

Participant Information and Consent Form

Project title: Research Ethics and integrity for the GREEN transition

Project acronym: RE4GREEN

European Commission Horizon Europe Grant Agreement no.: 101131706

Task 2.2 Interview Consent Form

Introduction

You have been invited to participate in interviews for the RE4GREEN project. Before you can decide to participate in this study, you must understand its nature, significance, scope, as well as the risks and potential benefits. Please read the following information carefully. If you have any uncertainties, questions, or require further information, please contact us.

What is RE4GREEN?

Environmental and climate-related challenges are global and reach all sectors of society. However, research and innovation (R&I) activities that address these challenges may carry substantial unintended implications. **RE4GREEN aims to contribute to a European Research Area ethics and integrity framework for R&I activities designed to reduce the risk from such implications and to support the transition to a sustainable economy and society as envisioned by the European Green Deal.** RE4GREEN will reflect diverse stakeholder views and relate them to cross-cutting environmental and climate-related ethics issues by applying a bottom-up social lab methodology. RE4GREEN's framework will consist of operational research ethics and integrity guidelines, recommendations, and training materials for researchers, ethics and integrity experts and advisors, and ethics reviewers to ensure R&I activities support the Green Transition.

Aim of this research activity

We are inviting you to participate in an interview to learn from your insights on climate and environmental ethics issues and relevant training needs in your area of research.

The primary aim of the RE4GREEN project is to create ethical guidance concerning climate and environmental ethics within Research and Innovation, drawing on insights from a diverse range of stakeholders. To achieve this objective, we will employ a Social Lab methodology. A “Social Laboratory,” or Social Lab for short, is a group of people brought together to tackle complex social problems. This approach necessitates thorough recruitment efforts to ensure the inclusion of all relevant stakeholders. Central to the recruitment process is the task of conducting interviews. These interviews will foster relationships and provide valuable insights to inform the project work.

The interview will occur online and is intended to last approximately 30-45 minutes.

Risks and benefits of participation

You may benefit from specialized training materials, guidelines and recommendations produced by the RE4GREEN project that address the specific ethical and integrity challenges you may encounter in your work.

It is expected that there will be no physical or psychological risks for your participation in the interview. However, the interview may address sensitive topics related to experiences in research ethics and integrity. To reduce emotional discomfort, you are encouraged to avoid speaking of specific names, organizations, and individuals. Social Labs facilitators have received training in inclusive and sensitive facilitation techniques to ensure a supportive and respectful environment during the interview.

Compensation

Please note that no compensation will be provided for your participation in the interview.

Data collection

Your name, affiliation, self-identified gender, sector and geography, and contact details will be the only personal data we process as part of this activity and will not be shared publicly. These data will be destroyed five years after the completion of the reporting phase at the end of the project, no later than June 2032.

An important component is to systematically collect and analyse the expert knowledge of relevant stakeholders on climate and environmental ethics and research integrity issues. For this purpose, we request to keep documentation of the interviews, as well as pseudonymised quotations. Results will be used for our systematic and scientific analysis of results, and will be pseudonymised, aggregated, and reported in summary form. It will not be possible to trace your personal data to any findings.

If you explicitly provide your consent below, audio and/or video recordings may be made during your interview. These recordings will be used solely to aid in the transcription of the interview and will enable us to pseudonymise the information shared during the interview. Pseudonymisation is when personal information gets replaced with fake names or codes to keep it private. If you do not provide your consent to record the interview, the interviewer will take handwritten notes instead.

The data gathered from the interviews will be pseudonymised using a random unique identifier. Results will be used to advance the work of the project in developing ethics and research integrity guidelines, reports to the European Commission, academic and popular publications, blog posts and conference presentations.

If you wish to be identified as a participant, this is also in your rights (e.g., an acknowledgment at the end of the report). If you agree to be acknowledged for your contribution to interviews, only your name and affiliation will be indicated at the end of the relevant public project report and publications. However, your data from the interview will still not be associated to any specific sections or quotations (unless you instruct otherwise).

Data processing

- The legal basis for data processing is your voluntary consent (Article 6(1)(a) GDPR and Article 9(2)(a) GDPR).
- The person responsible for data processing is Prof. Dr. Dirk Lanzerath at the German Reference Center for Ethics in the Life Sciences (DRZE) (+49 228 738110, re4green@drze.de)

Participation in the interview is voluntarily. You may stop participating at any time you want, without giving any reason. Data that relates to you will be destroyed and will not be used for the purpose of the project.

You have the right to request information about your personal data processed by us and to have any incorrect data rectified or erased. Subject to the provisions of the General Data Protection Regulation, you also have the right to request the restriction of the processing or the transfer of your personal data. In cases of suspected violation of the data protection provisions you can contact the Data Protection Authority (https://www.bfdi.bund.de/DE/Infothek/Anschriften_Links/anschriften_links-node.html).

You also have the right to withdraw your consent at any time, verbally or in writing, and to object to the processing of your data, without any disadvantage to you. If you withdraw your consent, no further data will be collected. You may also request the deletion of your data that has not been published. Please note that the withdrawal of consent will not affect the lawfulness of processing based on consent before its withdrawal and that your data may need to be further processed to prove compliance with the guidelines of good research practice.

The University of Bonn will not make any decision based solely on automated data processing which produces legal effects concerning you or similarly significantly affects you.

Storage of data

Your data will be handled securely at all times. We will store your personal data until five years after the end of the final reporting period to the European Commission. This means that any quotations and data will be deleted after the completion of the project plus reporting period and no later than June 2032.

Your personal data, including contact information, and any direct quotations will be stored on the individual secure servers of the University of Bonn and never transferred. Your Unique ID and name will be centrally coordinated within the Consortium to avoid duplication of contacts. Only your affiliation, self-identified gender, sector and geography will be transferred within the Consortium for the purposes of reporting to the European Commission in sensitive deliverables (e.g., on stakeholder participation). Only the anonymized summary reports of the interviews will be transferred within the Consortium for the purposes of research and analysis.

Whenever data is collected, stored, used, or shared, there are risks to confidentiality. These risks can't be completely avoided and increase as more data is connected. Social Lab facilitators will take every possible step, using the latest technology, to protect your privacy.

You have the right to request information from the University of Bonn about the personal data stored about you (including a free copy of the data). You may also request the correction of inaccurate data and, if necessary, the transfer of the data provided by you and the restriction of its processing. Please contact the University of Bonn for this information.

For concerns regarding data processing and compliance with data protection requirements, you can also contact the following data protection officers:

- a) The data protection officer of the University of Bonn: Dr. Jörg Hartmann (joerg.hartmann@uni-bonn.de)
- b) The data protection officer of the Austrian Institute of Technology (Social Lab coordinators): Michael Löffler (michael.loeffler@ait.ac.at)

You also have the right to lodge a complaint with a data protection supervisory authority. If you have concerns regarding the handling of your personal data, you can contact the following authorities:

State Commissioner for Data Protection and Freedom of Information North Rhine-Westphalia
PO Box 20 04 44
40102 Düsseldorf
Telephone exchange: +4921138424 - 0

Incidental findings

Although not anticipated, any incidental findings related to violations of research ethics and integrity that may arise during the Social Labs interviews will be treated with care. The University of Bonn will guide participants to the appropriate institutional, regional, or national authorities responsible for monitoring research ethics and integrity. Additionally, any unexpected findings will be promptly reported to the RE4GREEN management team at the University of Bonn to ensure transparency and accountability in addressing these matters. Throughout this process, the anonymity and autonomy of participants will be strictly respected.

Informed Consent Form

I, the undersigned, confirm that I have read and understood the information about the project, as provided in the information sheet. I have been given the opportunity to ask questions about my participation in the Social Lab interview. I am participating in this research voluntarily and I am free to end my participation at any time without negative consequences. I may refuse to answer any questions I do not wish to discuss. I understand that I will be asked to provide, as relevant, professional or personal views and that the record of my involvement in the research will be kept confidential and anonymized (unless otherwise instructed and permitted).

I understand that the results of the interview will be kept and irretrievably deleted five years after the relevant reports have been submitted, and no later than June 2032. I understand that the extracted data from this exercise (pseudonymised, unless otherwise requested) will be used as input to project reports (which will be submitted to the European Commission and made available publicly on the project website and in a public repository). The data may also be used for other related research outputs such as publications.

Under the General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (art. 13 and 14), the consortium has an obligation to inform of the purpose of the collection, use, storage, and retention of the information I have provided. I understand that the project will only collect information that is relevant to its activities. Any personal information will be stored on the University of Bonn's secure, enterprise level, password-protected internal servers, as described above. Anonymized information, as described above, will be accessible to only those involved in the RE4GREEN project or in sensitive reporting documents to the European Commission. The project will not transfer my personal information to third parties outside the project.

I also have the right of access to my personal data, the right to obtain the rectification of my data. I further have the right to obtain the restriction of processing or the right to transmit my data to another controller under the specific terms of the General Data Protection Regulation. In addition, I have the right to object to the processing of my personal data. If I am of the opinion that my data is processed unlawfully, I have the right to file a complaint with a supervisory authority.

I understand that this research conforms to European Commission guidelines.

I am free to contact Prof. Dr. Dirk Lanzerath, coordinator of the RE4GREEN project, about any queries relating to my data or the project itself. His e-mail address is re4green@drze.de and telephone number is +49 228 738110. I may also contact the local lab leader, (email address).

Additional disclosure options:

- I agree to record the interview using a recording device.

Yes No

To receive further communication about the project:

- I agree to be included in the RE4GREEN stakeholder database in order to be contacted by project partners for future activities of the project. I accept that RE4GREEN partners store my contact information for this purpose and for the duration of the project.

Yes No

- I agree to receive further communication by email related to activities of the RE4GREEN project and accept that RE4GREEN partners store my contact information for this purpose and for the duration of the project.

Yes No

- I agree to my details being retained by RE4GREEN partners to be contacted for a future study on research ethics and integrity training.

Yes No

Name

Organisation

Date and place

Signature

Annex 2 – Workshop Consent Form

Participant Information and Consent Form

Project title: Research Ethics and integrity for the GREEN transition

Project acronym: RE4GREEN

European Commission Horizon Europe Grant Agreement no.: 101131706

Task 2.2 Social Lab Workshop Participant Information and Consent Form

Contact person for questions about RE4GREEN:

Prof. Dr. Dirk Lanzerath

German Reference Center for Ethics in the Life Sciences (DRZE)

Bonner Talweg 57

53113 Bonn

+49 228 738110

re4green@drze.de

Contact person for your social lab:

Introduction

You have been invited to participate in the RE4GREEN Social Labs. Before you can decide to participate in this study, you must understand its nature, significance, scope, as well as the risks and potential benefits. Please read the following information carefully. If you have any uncertainties, questions, or require further information, please contact us.

What is RE4GREEN?

Environmental and climate-related challenges are global and reach all sectors of society. However, research and innovation (R&I) activities that address these challenges may carry substantial unintended implications. **RE4GREEN aims to contribute to a European Research Area ethics and integrity framework for R&I activities designed to reduce the risk from such implications and to support the transition to a sustainable economy and society as envisioned by the European Green Deal.** RE4GREEN will reflect diverse stakeholder views and relate them to cross-cutting environmental and climate-related ethics issues by applying a bottom-up social lab methodology. RE4GREEN's framework will consist of operational research ethics and integrity guidelines, recommendations, and training materials for researchers, ethics and integrity experts and advisors, and ethics reviewers to ensure R&I activities support the Green Transition.

Aim of this research activity

We are inviting your participation in the RE4GREEN [Social Lab XXXX] to learn from your insights on climate and environmental ethics issues and relevant training needs in your area of research.

A “Social Laboratory,” or Social Lab for short, is a group of people brought together to tackle complex social problems. Just as scientific and technical laboratories push the boundaries of human knowledge, Social Labs aim to push boundaries in addressing social issues. These labs explore complex issues, going beyond traditional laboratory boundaries to address matters like culture, values, politics, and the environment.

When applied to research and innovation (R&I) contexts, Social Labs provide a proven method for engaging diverse stakeholders over time to understand and address important societal issues. In the RE4GREEN project, Social Labs bring together experts from various fields to explore environmental and climate research ethics and integrity challenges, supporting efforts for a greener future.

Details about your participation

As a participant in the RE4GREEN Social Labs, you will be invited to participate in three online workshops and one in-person workshop. Your expertise and experience will help us develop a deeper understanding of:

- **Issues:** Climate and environmental ethics and research integrity challenges in your field
- **Responses:** Ways in which your field is working to or might respond to such challenges
- **Resources:** The kinds of trainings, guidelines, and otherwise) that you might need to respond to such challenges in your research or practice

The approximate timing and duration of each Social Lab workshop is as follows:

- Online, workshop 1, approximately 4-5 hours with breaks, December 2024 or February 2025: Climate and environmental ethics and integrity issues and training needs
- Online workshop 2, approximately 4-5 hours with breaks, March or early April 2025: Responses to climate and environmental ethics and integrity issues
- Online workshop 3, approximately 4-5 hours with breaks, June 2025: Guidelines, recommendations, and trainings to support responses to climate and environmental ethics and integrity issues
- In-person workshop 1, approximately 1.5 days, travel and accommodation expenses covered, September or October 2025: Climate and environmental ethics and environmental risk assessments; responding to the European Commission's "Do No Significant Harm" principle.

Risks and benefits of participation

Your participation will allow you to network and interact with researchers from across Europe that have a variety of areas of expertise, sectoral experience, and backgrounds. In addition, you may benefit from specialized training materials, guidelines and recommendations produced by the RE4GREEN project that address the specific ethical and integrity challenges you may encounter in your work.

It is expected that there will be no physical or psychological risks for your participation in the Social Labs. However, the workshops may address sensitive topics related to experiences in research ethics and integrity. To reduce emotional discomfort, you are encouraged to avoid speaking of specific names, organizations, and individuals. Social Labs facilitators have received training in inclusive and sensitive facilitation techniques to ensure a supportive and respectful environment during the workshops.

Compensation

You will be reimbursed for any travel and accommodation costs incurred while participating in the in-person Social Lab. The German Reference Center for Ethics in the Life Sciences (DRZE) at the University of Bonn will initiate this payment via bank transfer following the workshop.

Please note that no other compensation will be provided for your participation in the study.

Data collection

Your name, affiliation, self-identified gender, sector and geography, and contact details will be the only personal data we process as part of this activity and will not be shared publicly. These data will be destroyed five years after the completion of the reporting phase at the end of the project, no later than June 2032.

An important component is to systematically collect and analyse the expert knowledge of relevant stakeholders on climate and environmental ethics and research integrity issues. For this purpose, we request to keep documentation

of workshop activities and notes from facilitation, as well as pseudonymised quotations from participants during the workshop. Results will be used for our systematic and scientific analysis of results, and will be pseudonymised, aggregated, and reported in summary form. It will not be possible to trace your personal data to any findings.

If you explicitly provide your consent below, audio and/or video recordings may be made during the workshops. These recordings will be used solely to aid in the transcription of the workshops and will enable us to pseudonymise the information shared during the workshops. Pseudonymisation is when personal information gets replaced with fake names or codes to keep it private. If you do not provide your consent to record the workshop, the facilitators will take handwritten notes instead.

All Social Lab workshops are convened under [Chatham House Rule](#): “When a meeting, or part thereof, is held under the Chatham House Rule, participants are free to use the information received, but neither the identity nor the affiliation of the speaker(s), nor that of any other participant, may be revealed.”

The data gathered from the Social Lab workshops will be pseudonymised using a random unique identifier. Results will be used to advance the work of the project in developing ethics and research integrity guidelines, reports to the European Commission, academic and popular publications, blog posts and conference presentations.

If you wish to be identified as a participant, this is also in your rights (e.g., an acknowledgment at the end of the report). If you agree to be acknowledged for your contribution to the workshops, only your name and affiliation will be indicated at the end of the relevant public project report and publications. However, your data from workshop activities will still not be associated to any specific sections or quotations (unless you instruct otherwise).

Data processing

- The legal basis for data processing is your voluntary consent (Article 6(1)(a) GDPR and Article 9(2)(a) GDPR).
- The person responsible for data processing is Prof. Dr. Dirk Lanzerath at the German Reference Center for Ethics in the Life Sciences (DRZE) (+49 228 738110, re4green@drze.de)

Participation in the Social Lab is voluntarily. You may stop participating at any time you want, without giving any reason. Data that relates to you will be destroyed and will not be used for the purpose of the project.

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The University of Bonn will not make any decision based solely on automated data processing which produces legal effects concerning you or similarly significantly affects you.

Storage of data

Your data will be handled securely at all times. We will store your personal data until five years after the end of the final reporting period to the European Commission. This means that any quotations and data will be deleted after the completion of the project plus reporting period and no later than June 2032.

Your personal data, including contact information, and any direct quotations will be stored on the individual secure servers of the University of Bonn and never transferred. Your Unique ID and name will be centrally coordinated within the Consortium to avoid duplication of contacts. Only your affiliation, self-identified gender, sector and geography will be transferred within the Consortium for the purposes of reporting to the European Commission in sensitive deliverables (e.g., on stakeholder participation). Only the anonymized summary reports of the Social Lab workshops will be transferred within the Consortium for the purposes of research and analysis.

Whenever data is collected, stored, used, or shared, there are risks to confidentiality. These risks can't be completely avoided and increase as more data is connected. Social Lab facilitators will take every possible step, using the latest technology, to protect your privacy.

You have the right to request information from the University of Bonn about the personal data stored about you (including a free copy of the data). You may also request the correction of inaccurate data and, if necessary, the transfer of the data provided by you and the restriction of its processing. Please contact the University of Bonn for this information.

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- a) The data protection officer of the University of Bonn: Dr. Jörg Hartmann (joerg.hartmann@uni-bonn.de)
- b) The data protection officer of the Austrian Institute of Technology (Social Lab coordinators): Michael Löffler (michael.loeffler@ait.ac.at)

You also have the right to lodge a complaint with a data protection supervisory authority. If you have concerns regarding the handling of your personal data, you can contact the following authorities:

State Commissioner for Data Protection and Freedom of Information North Rhine-Westphalia
PO Box 20 04 44
40102 Düsseldorf
Telephone exchange: +4921138424 - 0

Incidental findings

Although not anticipated, any incidental findings related to violations of research ethics and integrity that may arise during the Social Labs workshops will be treated with care. The University of Bonn will guide participants to the appropriate institutional, regional, or national authorities responsible for monitoring research ethics and integrity. Additionally, any unexpected findings will be promptly reported to the RE4GREEN management team at the University of Bonn to ensure transparency and accountability in addressing these matters. Throughout this process, the anonymity and autonomy of participants will be strictly respected.

Insurance

Please note that there will be no insurance provided for your journey to the in-person Social Lab workshop or your stay at the study site.

Consent Form

I, the undersigned, confirm that I have read and understood the information about the project, as provided in the information sheet. I have been given the opportunity to ask questions about my participation in the Social Labs. I am participating in this research voluntarily and I am free to end my participation at any time without negative consequences. I may refuse to answer any questions I do not wish to discuss. I understand that I will be asked to provide, as relevant, professional or personal views and that the record of my involvement in the research will be kept confidential and anonymized (unless otherwise instructed and permitted).

I understand that the results of workshop activities will be kept and irretrievably deleted five years after the relevant reports have been submitted, and no later than June 2032. I understand that the extracted data from this exercise (pseudonymised, unless otherwise requested) will be used as input to project reports (which will be submitted to the European Commission and made available publicly on the project website and in a public repository). The data may also be used for other related research outputs such as publications.

Under the General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (art. 13 and 14), the consortium has an obligation to inform of the purpose of the collection, use, storage, and retention of the information I have provided. I understand that the project will only collect information that is relevant to its activities. Any personal information will be stored on the University of Bonn's secure, enterprise level, password-protected internal servers, as described above. Anonymized information, as described above, will be accessible to only those involved in the RE4GREEN project or in sensitive reporting documents to the European Commission. The project will not transfer my personal information to third parties outside the project.

I also have the right of access to my personal data, the right to obtain the rectification of my data. I further have the right to obtain the restriction of processing or the right to transmit my data to another controller under the specific terms of the General Data Protection Regulation. In addition, I have the right to object to the processing of my personal data. If I am of the opinion that my data is processed unlawfully, I have the right to file a complaint with a supervisory authority.

I understand that this research conforms to European Commission guidelines.

I am free to contact Prof. Dr. Dirk Lanzerath, coordinator of the RE4GREEN project, about any queries relating to my data or the project itself. His e-mail address is re4green@drze.de and telephone number is +49 228 738110. I may also contact the data protection officer, XXX, and local lab leader, XXX.

Additional disclosure options:

- I wish to include the name of my organization in the list of organizations participating in RE4GREEN Social Labs.
Yes No
- I wish to include my name in the list of participants in RE4GREEN Social Labs.
Yes No
- I agree to record the workshop using a recording device.

Yes No

To receive further communication about the project:

- I agree to be included in the RE4GREEN stakeholder database in order to be contacted by project partners for future activities of the project. I accept that RE4GREEN partners store my contact information for this purpose and for the duration of the project.

Yes No

- I agree to receive further communication by email related to activities of the RE4GREEN project and accept that RE4GREEN partners store my contact information for this purpose and for the duration of the project.

Yes No

- I agree to my details being retained by RE4GREEN partners to be contacted for a future study on research ethics and integrity training.

Yes No

Name

Organisation

Date and place

Signature

Annex 3 – Workshops 2 responses relating to the GT

Clean, affordable, and secure energy

Advancing

- Educating the Next Generation of Scientists and Engineers (SL2, RTO)
- Materials Innovation for Energy Efficiency (SL2, RTO)
- Support for Renewables through Advanced Materials (SL2, RTO)
- Improve framework conditions for renewable energy technologies, onshore, offshore wind and solar power (SL4, Energy Organization participant)
- An electrification of society to move away from fossil fuels (SL4, Energy Organization participant)
- Work to improve grid integration in [Country] and improving overall grid infrastructure on a European level (SL4, Energy Organization participant)
- We provide state of the art models and data to assess impacts of wind power through an online interactive map that is fully open. This brings data that is usually only available to experts to a wider public and hopefully would help to simplify discussions about new wind farm projects (SL4, University researcher)
- we assess together with citizens and stakeholders of disadvantaged neighborhoods how would it be possible to transform their neighborhoods into positive energy districts (SL4, University researcher)
- We develop tools to simplify and support the creation and growth of energy communities. (SL4, University researcher)
- Batteries are the keystone to resilient energy infrastructure (SL4, University researcher)
- Support the production of env. Friendly [wind] energy (SL4, Education and research)
- Prepare qualified workforce for green energy sector (SL4, Education and research)
- Find strategies and policies & recommend and implement just(er) energy systems (prod. & consumption) (SL4, Education and research)
- Improve methods of sustainability Assessment (SL4, Education and research)
- Supporting advancement of policy and regulatory frameworks to enable RE development and RE integration (SL4, Government participant)
- Capacity building across public sector entities to further energy transition (be that energy planning, system analysis, sector reform, market development, RE procurement, etc. etc.) (SL4, Government participant)
- Sharing lessons learnt from decades of RE development and sector and policy reforms, in the hope of empowering other governments to make informed decisions and avoid pitfalls (SL4, Government participant)
- By a much more directed use of our resources we might be able to save on input-energy into the plant systems we cultivate - be it fossil fuels or even in terms of usage of renewable energy (SL6 applied researcher)

Hindering

- Resource, intensive research (SL2, RTO)
- Slow technology transfer (SL2, RTO)
- Negative results about technologies (technical/economical) unfeasibility could be seen as a general unfeasibility of the energy transition (e.g. renewable fuels) (SL4, University researcher)

- Decrease of 'wild' areas; increase of human intervention in the ecosystem (SL4, Education and research)
- Recognizing the need to balance policy priorities - JET - economic growth - jobs... => cannot prioritize green energy transition in vacuum (SL4 Government participant)
- sometimes failure to engage critically in debate about environmental implications of energy development - even RE is not without negative impacts (SL4 Government participant)
- trade-offs between environmental and climate priorities (SL4 Government participant)
- at a smaller and more day-to-day scale ... Global cooperation requires global travel... - while there are strict requirements around travel modes for more local travel, there is little critical reflection on what is seen as an inherent characteristic of the work (international flying) (SL4 Government participant)
- The development of renewable energy infrastructure may infer in ecological process and degrade or fragment natural ecosystems. (SL5 Research institute participant)
- A lot of international meetings, congresses and workshops are still on an in-presence basis with high Co2 footprint. (SL5 Marine Research institute participant)
- growing demand of energy because of digitization (but applies probably for all research and non-research areas) (SL6, University participant II)

Sustainable Industry and Circular Economy

Advancing

- Funding basic research that may provide scientific basis for sustainable developments (SL1, Research Funder)
- We discourage use of carbon credits...greenwashing (SL1, Large multi-national company)
- We are discussing the way to use templates for carbon footprint tracking (SL1, Large multi-national company)
- We are moving from paper medical referrals to QR codes/mobile cell phones for our research participants for their treatment services (SL1, Researcher)
- Manage Research project in AI and recycling (SL2, HEI)
- Get more in Date issues with respect open data (SL2, HEI)
- Supporting SME in getting in projects addressing green deal, most of them in circular economy (SL2, HEI)
- Development of clean energy or energy vectors production from alternative technologies and processes, focused on sustainability (SL2, HEI)
- Development of circular processes (e.g., biorefineries), that target zero emissions and are fed by residues/by-products, producing high-value products (SL2, CSO)
- We promote reuse and repair of EEE through repair events and by sharing information about how to diagnose and repair equipment. We also implemented a training to teach people to diagnose and repair small EEE. Regarding plastics, we have already did awareness raising campaigns about disposable cups (because [municipality] banned plastic disposable cups, but allows other disposable materials) . And we also developed a study about the positive environmental impacts of reuse systems in food packaging, e-commerce and washing products. (SL2, CSO)
- Development of safer, more sustainable and affordable biotechnologies, alternatives to conventional ones (e.g., bio-based against fuel-based ones) (SL2, RTO)
- Valorization of residues and by-products from industries (e.g., food, feed, CO2) to use them as feedstock for (bio)production of new food products. This ends in advantages in raw

material needs, auto sufficiency, net or even negative emissions, and environmentally-friendly processes (SL2, RTO)

- We support space up-stream project to be more sustainable - we raise awareness for the topic and help them increase positive impact in their business model and reduce negative impact. (SL2 participant working in space exploration technologies)
- the (often still unsustainable) up-stream sector provides the down-stream area which offers data to foster sustainability projects and environmental data (SL2 participant working in space exploration technologies)
- Development of biofuels (SL2 participant working in space exploration technologies)
- We promote better practices in different companies by creating workshops or programs to raise awareness about the impact of pollution on our environment. (SL5, NGO)
- Demonstrate new (sustainable) ways e.g. production processes, products (SL6 technology association participant)
- Demonstrate problems with regulations which hinders Green Transition from industry perspective (SL6 technology association participant)
- Demonstrate interrelations - like value chain network (SL6 technology association participant)
- Strengthening (vocational) education & skills development by integrating bioeconomy topics into curricula and vocational training (SL6 Transformation hub participant)
- Aims at uncovering (un)conscious barriers that prevent consumers and producers from making sustainable choices, while also recognizing key drivers that encourage adoption (SL6, University participant)
- Research on sustainability labeling, messaging strategies, and consumer perception aims at developing communication strategies to achieve these goals (SL6, University participant)
- helping innovative "green" startups survive economically, we help spread the idea that green and economically viable can go hand-in-hand (SL6 Applied research participant)

Hindering

- Work needs a lot of traveling for B2B contact (SL2, HEI)
- technical progress has always risks of being successful, so what is the other side of the coin (SL2, HEI)
- Bio based Material is there a constrain with food or biodiversity (SL2, HEI)
- The materials (launching infrastructure, propulsion systems, satellite...) are very resource intensive (SL2 participant working in space exploration technologies)
- Especially the up-stream space sector requires a lot of energy (launching) and non-sustainable materials and they have difficulties finding better alternatives (SL2 participant working in space exploration technologies)
- Sometimes research institutes don't want to work with some high impact companies and maybe it would be better to work together with commitment. (SL5 Marine Research institute participant)
- Technology, given the freedom to choose based on only data may find options extremely favourable that might collide with other goals such as circular economy or even eliminating pollution or sustainable food production itself. The degrees of freedom may not be limited by our human interpretations or our static goals. (SL6 applied researcher)
- Highlighting consumer skepticism, price sensitivity, or resistance to sustainable products, might reveal significant adoption challenges, that might lead to cautious investment by businesses (SL6, University participant)

- Highlights the trade-offs consumers for example need to make. Consumers often prioritize convenience over sustainability. Partially sustainable solutions as an incremental step, slowing down transformative change or leading to conservative approaches. (SL6, University participant)
- Sustainable communication challenges; very product-consumer-...-specific. (SL6, University participant)
- It is not always the "greenest" solution that is the most economically viable (SL6 Applied researcher)
- Sometimes, solutions are pursued that make no sense or are greenwashing (customer is king) (SL6 Applied researcher)

Sustainable Living (Building and Renovation)

Advancing

- We share information on how municipalities and citizens can prevent generating waste and promote circular economy as a tool to decrease the amount of waste and, therefore, the quantity needed to be managed and recycled (also, we participated in talks and share with the municipality the need to decrease the volume of waste instead on focusing on buying more trucks and hiring more people to pick up the waste in the city) (SL2 participant)

Hindering

-

Safer and More Sustainable Chemicals

Advancing

- We follow and localize the NIH research guidelines which include environmental safety protocols for safe disposal of hazardous materials (for harm reduction supplies) (SL1, Researcher)
- production and utilization of safer chemicals and compounds that produce lower environmental impact than conventional ones. (e.g., synthetic surfactants against biosurfactants) (SL2 participant)
- there are many innovations on safer processing methods eliminating nasty chemicals that are being developed (SL4, University researcher)

Hindering

- there are still many nasty chemicals that are unavoidable. e.g. fluorides and nickel (SL4, University researcher)

Sustainable Food Production

Advancing

- Computer vision and image analysis and other AI solutions allow for automatic analysis of crops, harvest, pests, need for pesticides, or fertilizers. This allows to use fewer resources in a more precise fashion, yielding higher harvests. Advanced robotics + AI allow for automatic weeding. Similar systems are used in forestry (SL2, Researcher in AI)

- The use of smart technologies tackles one of the specifically agriculture-related goals of pesticide-reduction. We have formulated the goal of a 50% reduction per-se and still need to find ways to actually be able to achieve that while maintaining food-safety. Still, the use of smart technology seems to be one of the absolute key parts in this transition. (SL6 Applied researcher)
- Collaboration with farmers to find together nature-based solutions: smart (or no) pesticide use, sustain/support biodiversity (Mischkulturanbau) more economic gain, food production, less pollution, less biodiversity loss, more resilient agriculture (SL6 applied researcher)
- Sustainable agriculture: controlling agricultural non-point pollution (community-based management) in South Korea--I conducting capacity building programs and model program including incentives (SL6 University researcher)
- Aims at helping that bio-based products, sustainable agriculture, and circular economy solutions move from lab to market by better understanding decision-making processes (SL6, University participant)

Hindering

- AI systems consume a lot of energy which can be produced in various ways, however these systems require resources that could be spent elsewhere. Some of the energy is not green causing additional strain on the environment (SL2, Researcher in AI)
- AI and tech is not always something that traditional farmers trust or understand; leaving these tools available to intensive farmers (SL2, Researcher in AI)

Eliminating Pollution

Advancing

- Raising awareness among researchers about the CO2-footprint of their research (SL1, Research Funder)
- Reducing the CO2 footprint of our own offices and operations (SL1, Research Funder)
- We incorporate green research practices, like sustainable fieldwork methods, eco-friendly alternatives for harm reduction supplies (SL1, Researcher)
- We are reducing travel for fieldwork and training by using virtual tools and online surveys (SL1, Researcher)
- Organizing cleanups makes people more aware of the problem so they can take action, and also the removed kilos are no longer a pollutant in the environment. (SL5, NGO)
- With Ocean Literacy we train people to understand the importance of reducing pollutants in the environment. Working with schools and universities to make sure generations of the future are aligned with this. (SL5, NGO)
- We support the [Country] Ocean Literacy Network through board membership. (SL5 Government participant)
- Support of freshwater ecosystem restoration and conservation efforts. (SL5 Research institute participant)
- Identification of anthropogenic impacts and pressures on freshwater ecosystems (SL5 Research institute participant)
- Environmental modelling to predict the impacts and benefits of a pollution or ecological restoration scenario. (SL5 Research institute participant)

- Analysis of water pollutants and development of nature-based solutions for wastewater treatment. (SL5 Research institute participant)
- Drought hazard modelling at regional scale to inform policy makers. (SL5 Research institute participant)
- Studying marine ecology, protecting biodiversity (SL5 Marine Research institute participant)
- Promoting Ocean Literacy, reflecting on Ocean's influence in people and people's influence in the ocean (SL5 Marine Research institute participant)
- Raising awareness in marine pollution (e.g. wet wipes tangled in gorgonians in Barcelona) (SL5 Marine Research institute participant)
- Developing awareness and educational materials (SL5 Marine Research institute participant) by deploying proven water security solutions such as fit-to-purpose technologies (SL5 University researcher)
- The use of smart technology in agriculture gives us the chance to get a deeper insight into the very agile biosystem that is soil and plant growth. By this deep insight we should be able to make more sufficient planning and therefore eliminate pollution by over- or underdosing of what our plants and soils need. (SL6 applied researcher)

Hindering

- As scientific excellence is the main criterion for funding, the research we fund may have a significant CO2 footprint (SL1, Research Funder)
- Work trips from our staff are necessary, but also add to the CO2 footprint (SL1, Research Funder)
- Academic travel is not always environmentally friendly (SL1, Higher Education Institute participant)
- Sometimes the limitation is funding, so there are more challenges to fulfill our goal when there is no support from government or companies. (SL5, NGO)
- Data storage and processing consumes energy. (SL5 Government participant)
- Our work involves a significant amount of travel both nationally and sometimes internationally, thus consuming resources. (SL5 Government participant)
- We still rely quite heavily on printed resources and materials for training and data dissemination. (SL5 Government participant)
- Research and actions in research institutes depend on funding and research priorities and sometimes important problems cannot be properly addressed or count with researcher's vision because of this kind of limitations. (SL5 Marine Research institute participant)
- There are still not enough applied projects or transfer projects at my institute, these projects should be enhanced and promoted and more appreciated in research careers to be able to help with green transition goals. (SL5 Marine Research institute participant)

Sustainable mobility

Advancing

- batteries are crucial to electric vehicles (SL4, University researcher)
- Decreasing emissions from transportation by electrifying mobility applications with the help of batteries (SL4, Research performing organization)
- Replacing critical raw materials by renewable and sustainable materials, e.g., using biobased carbon for batteries (in the anode to replace mined graphite, for example). (SL4, Research performing organization)

- Developing processing methods (for batteries), which consume less energy and use less/no toxic solvents. (SL4, Research performing organization)
- Ensuring that there are solutions to recycle batteries (SL4, Research performing organization)

Hindering

- electric cars being heavier increases air pollution from tyres (SL4, University researcher)
- Batteries need raw materials, which are mined. This will have a negative environmental impact locally (even though the overall impact is positive) (SL4, Research performing organization)
- There is a risk that increased battery use will generate a need to perform deep sea mining, which can contain unknown risks for marine environment. (SL4, Research performing organization)
- Batteries use e.g. PFAS materials and there is a risk that these forever chemicals will leak into the environment. We are trying to find replacement materials but it is not so easy. (SL4, Research performing organization)

Climate adaptation

Advancing

- batteries will be the key to off grid systems which will enable climate resilience much better than a larger electricity grid (SL4, University researcher)

Hindering

- making batteries currently relies on a global supply chain which is vulnerable to global shocks (SL4, University researcher)

Restore biodiversity

Advancing

- Restore biodiversity by bioremediating soils/water/sediments in natural locations (SL2 participant)
- Supporting data collection and sharing relating to climate impacts and biodiversity (SL5 Government participant)
- Collecting data to provide evidence base on biodiversity loss. (SL5 Government participant)
- Providing evidence base for decisions on biodiversity conservation. (SL5 Government participant)
- Supporting data collection and sharing relating to water quality and biodiversity (SL5 Government participant)
- By utilizing smart technologies we may find solutions to problems connected to biodiversity. E.g. smart farming equipment may make it possible to select between harmful weeds and those supporting beneficial insect. (SL6 applied researcher)
- agroecological approach (multiple ecosystem services and income) - conducting country case analysis and developing guidelines of agroforestry projects (SL6 University researcher)

- Urban forests and urban agriculture as nature-based solution (climate mitigation, food supply, human health, social safety) - examining enabling conditions and constraining conditions for adopting and implementing urban agriculture/examining urban forest governance including multi-stakeholders' interaction (SL6 University researcher)
- Global biodiversity assessment (IPBES): analyzing policy instruments/enabling conditions & environment in several countries (SL6 University researcher)
- Promoting regional bioeconomy through innovation and circular systems. (SL6, Transformation hub participant)
- Investigating consumer acceptance of bio-based materials (e.g., lignin-based textiles, cellulose packaging) and thus supports the transition from fossil-based to renewable materials (SL6, University participant)
- reviewing and sharing good practices of restoration on forested peatlands (SL6, University participant II)
- educating the young generation on how the green transition challenges may be tackled in the forest sector (SL6, University participant II)
- interacting with (and leading such interaction) companies and co-constructing and evaluating sustainable business models in forestry (SL6, University participant II)

Hindering

- the need for domestic minerals has often overruled environmental interests in order to mine for graphite or nickel etc. (SL4, University researcher)
- networking and knowledge exchange work with increased use of digital tools for forest planning and environmental communication (in particular AI) will add to the energy demand and question resource efficiency (SL6, University participant II)
- research and communication to scale up nature restoration for biodiversity goals may in next decades increase greenhouse gas emissions (SL6, University participant II)
- innovation collaboration may foster incremental innovations, while more radical ones would be needed instead. (SL6, University participant II)

Just transition

Advancing

- We develop projects that aims a just transition to sustainable, fair and strong society (SL2 Researcher in AI)
- Many insights in sustainability require stepping beyond considerations of markets, efficiency and technical solutions. My contribution is often the articulation of such 'beyonds'. (SL4, Social science energy security researcher)
- At points, my work contributes to the inclusion of stakeholders and voices that are not naturally heard in processes of governance and management. This inclusion is crucial to achieve solutions that are democratically and socio-culturally sound. (SL4, Social science energy security researcher) . (SL4, Social science energy security researcher)
- By improving water security that supports human well-being, socioeconomic development, and environmental health (SL5 University researcher)
- By promoting empowerment and participation in community water decision-making (SL5 University researcher)
- by advancing measurement and monitoring of household water insecurity (SL5 University researcher)

- Supporting regional transition in the Rhenish mining region toward sustainability (SL6 Transformation hub participant)
- Facilitating cross-sector collaboration between industry, research, citizens and policymakers to enable systemic transformation (SL6 Transformation hub participant)
- Encouraging community involvement in regional transformation by supporting local initiatives and inclusive decision-making (SL6 Transformation hub participant)
- leading and doing conceptual and empirical research to understand what is just in sustainability transition (SL6, University participant II)

Hindering

- Context often commands that solutions 'fit' with existing structures and organizations. This means that it ultimately may contribute to the continuation of those structures, including their extractivist/non-sustainable aspects. (SL4, Social science energy security researcher)
- Travelling is the guilty secret of academics. We have exactly the large carbon-footprint that we often argue against.
- Sometimes we (SSH) academics make things perhaps a bit too difficult. Sometimes it might be better to simply get things done, even if there are some unresolved complexities pending and the solution not entirely perfect. (SL4, Social science energy security researcher)
- Extremely advanced technology in the agricultural sector e.g. robots may make the job sector for human workers more challenging. This is particularly fueled by the fact that tech-systems may be able to take over jobs that humans are incapable of. (SL6, applied researcher)
- Multi-stakeholder discussions can slow decision-making. Conflicting interest can delay consensus enormously. (SL6, University participant)

